

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 1.6

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101081883.

Start date of project: 1st December 2022

Duration: 48 months

Deliverable 1.6 Progress in set up of pilot regions

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 1.6

Deliverable details	
Work Package Title	WP1 Blueprinting the regional clusters
Task Number	Task 1.1: Set up, operation, demonstration and validation in pilot regions
Deliverable Number	D1.6
Deliverable Title	Progress in set up of pilot regions
Revision Number	2
Responsible Organisation	AGR
Author(s)	Carsten Beneker, Gerardo González, Nicola Parfitt, Enno Schröder, Jenna Senecal, Guillermo Moreno Ortega
Due Date	Friday, May 31st, 2024
Delivered Date	Friday, May 31st, 2024
Reviewed by	Carsten Beneker, Anita Beblek
Dissemination level	PU - public
Please cite as	Beneker, González, Parfitt, Senecal, D1.6 rev1, Progress in set up of pilot regions, 2024, P2Green consortium. Accessible at p2green.eu
Contact person EC	Sofia Pachini

Contributing partners	
1.	AGRATHAER GMBH – Germany (Coordinator)
2.	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV – Germany
3.	VILLE DE PARIS – France
4.	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN – Ireland
5.	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET - Sweden
6.	COPENHAGEN BUSINESS SCHOOL - Denmark
7.	LUONNONVARAKESKUS - Finland
8.	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND MAYNOOTH - Ireland
9.	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - Greece
10.	BIOAZUL, SL - Spain
11.	CIP CITIZENS IN POWER - Cyprus
12.	ECOVILLAGE HANNOVER EG – Germany (terminated)
13.	GOLDEIMER GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH - Germany
14.	INSTITUT D'ARQUITECTURA AVANCADA DE CATALUNYA - Spain
15.	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH) - Germany
16.	FUNDACION CENTRO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONES DEL AGUA - Spain
17.	SUN GLOBAL CHEMICALS SERVICES SL - Spain
18.	IRIDRA SRL - Italy
19.	ECOLE NATIONALE DES PONTS ET CHAUSSEES - France
20.	KOZGAZDASAG- ES REGIONALIS TUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT - Hungary
21.	HAFENCITY UNIVERSITAT HAMBURG - Germany

22.	SUSTCHEM TECHNIKI SYMVOULEFTIKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA - Greece
23.	TRANSITION APS - Denmark
24.	TRIODOS BANK NV - Netherlands
25.	MOVERIM CONSULTING SPRL - Belgium
26.	SOCIEDAD AGRARIA DE TRANSFORMACION TROPS N 2803 DE RESPONSABILIDAD LIMITADA - Spain
27.	AGRI SMART DATA SL - Spain
28.	TOUCH DOWN GOTLAND AB - Sweden
29.	SANITATION360 AB - Sweden
30.	GOTLANDS BRYGGERI AB - Sweden
31.	AGUAS Y SANEAMIENTOS DE LA AXARQUIA SA - Spain
32.	VUNANEXUS - Switzerland

Table of Contents

Table of Figures	6
Table of Tables	8
Executive Summary	9
1 Background	11
1.1 Detachment of the nutrient circles in the 20th century	11
1.2 N- & P- emissions from current linear systems	14
1.3 Contaminants contained in wastewater	16
1.4 Sewage sludge management	16
1.5 Transformation approaches - from disposal to reclamation	18
Source separation	19
Water reuse	19
2 Circular value chain description and maturation status	22
2.1 Description and maturation of the Swedish circular value chain	23
Maturity of the urinal rental value chain	23
Maturity of the safe urine fertiliser production process	25
Maturity of field trials	26
Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the Swedish pilot	29
Governance readiness level for the Gotland Business Model	30
2.2 Description and maturation of the North German Plain circular value chain	32
Maturity of EVH/KWB premises and VunaNexus treatment installations	33
Maturity of Vagtshoff premises and Goldeimer treatment installations	35
Maturity of field trials at Vagtshoff	38
Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the German pilot	39
Governance readiness level of the North German Plain value chain	42
2.3 Description and maturation of the Spanish circular value chain	44
Maturity of water reclamation	46
Maturity of field trials	50
Maturity of Smart Fertigation Tool	56
Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the Spanish pilot region	60
Governance readiness level for the Axarquía model	62
3 Action plan	63

Project Number:

101081883

Project Acronym:

P2Green

Deliverable 1.6

3.1	Sweden implementation	64
3.2	Germany implementation.....	65
3.3	Spain implementation	67
4	References	71
5	ANNEX	a
5.1	Gantt Chart Pilot Region Gotland	a
5.2	Gantt Chart Pilot Region North German Plain	d
5.3	Gantt Chart Pilot Region La Axarquia	f

Table of Figures

Figure 1. The 2023 update to the nine key planetary boundaries, of which biogeochemical N- & P-flows as well as novel entities and freshwater change have transgressed the safe operating space. Licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 3.0. Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, based on analysis in Richardson et al 2023.....	12
Figure 2. Relative distribution of N per pathway in the member states (Eurostat, 2020)	14
Figure 3. Germany (#10) and Spain (#19) are both in the Top 20 of global cumulative total nitrogen input via wastewater (6.2 Tg N) (Tuholske et al. 2021).	15
Figure 4. Disposal of sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment by method of disposal in % of total (Eurostat, 2020).	18
Figure 5. Water reuse schemes per sector in Europe (Water Reuse Europe, 2020)....	20
Figure 6. Wastewater reuse allowance for agricultural irrigation in Member States (WISE, 2023).	21
Figure 7. Overview of the four different approaches and technology partners in P2Green.....	22
Figure 8. Photos of urine recycling process on Gotland. From the left a) Touch Down urinals rented out on Gotland for events; b) urine-based granulars with NPK of 15-2-4; c) The urine-based fertiliser is used with conventional farming equipment to grow barley; d) Beer brewed from barley fertilized with urine based fertiliser	24
Figure 9. Scheme of the value circle of the Gotland pilot region. Note: The Production Facility is to be built in 2025.	25
Figure 10. Installation of the urine drier that uses waste heat from cement production to concentrate the nutrients from urine by factor 25.	26
Figure 11. Farming equipment and set-up of field trials. From the left a) combi-seed drill where the barley and the urine pellets are buried into the soil 5-7 cm deep; b) visualisation of the 1.5 m wide replicates; and c) combine machinery used to harvest the barley grain.	27
Figure 12. The Swedish Pilot 2023 Field trial information. The image on the left is the schematic of how the treatments were placed in the field as a randomised treatment block design. Note: the frass is from another fertiliser treatment experiment at SLU and the results are not reported here. The table above contains specific details about the fertilisers used. The image of the barley field showcases how the field trial was in the middle of the farmers own field of barley. All barley was irrigated as needed.	28
Figure 13. Scheme of the value circle of the North German Plain pilot region.....	33
Figure 14. The bio-based fertiliser products produced in the Pilot Region North German Plain are Aurin®, which is an authorised fertilising product in Austria, Switzerland, (left photo by Vuna GmbH – vuna.ch) and (right) KIT, a compost made from solid human waste from dry toilets (right photo by Finizio GmbH – finizio.de).....	33
Figure 15. Images and schemes of the urine diverting flush toilet (UDFT) planned for EVH (above, courtesy of EOOS NEXT) and one urine diverting dry toilet (UDDT) type used by KWB subcontractor (below, courtesy of Finizio).....	34
Figure 16. Container-based VunaNexus urine treatment system at KWB premises.....	35

Figure 17. Event toilets as provided by project partner Goldeimer and bins used for solid waste logistics.....	36
Figure 18. 3-D image of the “Earthflow” container for highly automated and oxygen-controlled faeces composting at Vagtshoff (courtesy of Green Mountain Technologies)	37
Figure 19. Top – Container system for the sanitisation of dry toilet contents by thermophilic composting (step 1). Bottom: “Earthflow” container system for De- & Recomposition of organic waste by oxygen-controlled composting (step 2). Aeration pipes are covered by composting fleece and wood chips. Followed by biomass to be de- & repositioned.....	38
Figure 20. Top: Structure of the field trial near Hamburg with the arrangement of the measuring plots for various fertiliser treatments in a "Latin Square Design". Bottom: Field trails 3 weeks after seeding of summer rye. Perspective: eastwards, photo taken on 13.5.2024.....	39
Figure 21. Scheme of the value circle of the Axarquía pilot region.....	45
Figure 22. Flow diagram of tertiary treatment and disinfection.....	46
Figure 23. Raw wastewater entering the WWTP (left beaker), treated wastewater after secondary treatment in WWTP (middle beaker), and reclaimed water after tertiary treatment in water reclamation plant (right beaker).....	46
Figure 24. Discs filtration towers, control panel and pipeline towards mixing unit.....	47
Figure 25. Measurement tank with reclaimed water (upper pic) and submerged probes in the measurement tank for continuous monitoring of various physicochemical parameters (bottom images).....	48
Figure 26. Data logger and mixing unit with storage tanks for well water and reclaimed water.....	49
Figure 27. Test site construction and adaptation works.....	50
Figure 28. Scheme of fertigation treatments applied in avocado and mango trees.....	51
Figure 29. Avocado and mango plots.....	52
Figure 30. Scheme of experimental site and solution process.....	52
Figure 31. Collection of leaves in mango trees for foliar analysis.....	54
Figure 32. Windbreaks installed at the test site to protect avocado plants.....	55
Figure 33. Soils samples taken in avocado and mango plots.....	56
Figure 34. iTelemeter platform with graphs of humidity levels in soil registered by tensiometers in avocado and mango crops.....	58
Figure 35. Installation of one deposit for application of mineral fertilisers.....	59
Figure 36. Tensiometers (left), lysimeters (middle) and iTelemeter components installed (right).....	59
Figure 37. As of May 2024, 11 m ³ of urine has already been collected in Sweden together with SLU, S360 and Toa Bolaget (external project partner). The total goal for 2024 is 25 m ³	65

Table of Tables

Table 1. Nitrogen release data for each pilot regions country	15
Table 2. Field trial results 2023.....	29
Table 3. Identified challenges and barriers of the Swedish pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.....	29
Table 4. Identified challenges and barriers for urine valuation in the North German plain pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.	41
Table 5. Identified challenges and barriers for faeces valuation in the German pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.	42
Table 6. Comparison of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content between local water and reclaimed water in two different periods	50
Table 7. Fertilisation campaigns for avocado and mango crops	53
Table 8. Fertilising products applied to avocado and mango crops during fertilisation campaign	53
Table 9. Identified challenges and barriers of the Spanish pilot region rated by their perceived dimensions (red = higher and green = lower barrier).....	61
Table 10. Overview of tasks and deliverable dates and how they are proposed to be impacted by the on-going amendment	63
Table 11. Key Performance Indicators for the Swedish pilot region and progress planned.	65
Table 12. Key Performance Indicators of the pilot region North German Plain and progress planned.....	66
Table 13. Key Performance Indicators related to TRL in the Spanish pilot and progress planned.	67
Table 14. Additional Key Performance Indicators related to TRL in the Spanish pilot and progress planned.....	69
Table 15. Relevant indicators internally established by Spanish pilot and progress planned.	70

Executive Summary

The focus of this deliverable, integral to the P2Green project, is to provide a comprehensive update on the progress of Task 1.1: Set up, operation, demonstration, and validation in pilot regions. The pilot regions are located in Gotland, Sweden, the North German Plain (formerly Hamburg-Hanover), Germany and La Axarquia region, Spain, led by the pilot regions coordinators Sanitation 360, agrathaer, and Bioazul, respectively. Due to the termination of ecovillage hannover as a partner on the 15th of December 2023, they were replaced as an interim solution by AGR through a 1st Amendment. Currently a 2nd amendment process is on-going with the goal that the new partner Kreiswerke Barnim GmbH, located in the Federal State of Brandenburg, will form part of the German pilot region.

Our report is enriched with crucial outcomes, including progress tables for Key Performance Indicators and Governance Readiness Levels and executive project plans represented through Gantt Charts. The deliverable sets the stage for the Demonstration Report due in November 2025 (if due date will be updated based on amendment), showcasing validated prototypes from the three case studies (Deliverable 1.1).

The establishment and operationalisation of three P2Green pilot regions serve as dynamic environments for adapting, demonstrating, and maturing innovative circular nutrient flows keeping N & P cycles in balance. The primary objective is to create a nutrient cycle between water-waste infrastructure, that is connecting the nutrient output of urban areas with agricultural nutrient demands in an ecologically safe way, reducing the pollution from conventional sanitation systems and fertilisation. The pilot regions implement diverse systematic innovative technological, and system approaches to convert human sanitary waste into safe bio-based fertilisers for agricultural production, validated under real-life scale-up conditions.

As of this report, the pilot regions have operationalized different technology systems. The technology's full implementation is slated for March 2025 (updated Milestone 5), with the planning phase concluding with this report (Milestone 1).

The Swedish pilot region of Gotland: The urine-drying system has been designed and implemented by SLU and Sanitation360. The systems are being further optimized as a portable, off-grid design that can process the urine on-site or off-site. The urine is sourced via the mobile toilet provider Touch Down's existing network and maintenance contracts. In particular, this includes female and male urinals being dispatched to various events on Gotland. To be able to source more urine, the network has expanded to events on the mainland. Subcontracted farmers have used the pelletised recycling fertilisers in 2023 field trials (720 m²) with barley on Gotland, showcasing a very convincing fertility effect on the crops. The local brewery Gotland Bryggeri is validating the suitability of barley grown with urine-based fertiliser for beer production and, within the project time, produce commercially available beer to close the value chain.

The German pilot region of the North German Plain (formerly Hamburg-Hanover): The housing cooperative ecovillage hannover had planned for the installation of commercially available ceramic urine diverting flush toilets for 230 persons and planned to collect approximately 100 m³/yr urine. The urine was supposed to be processed at the ecovillage hannover in a central facility using the urine treatment system provided by VunaNexus (VN). Due to the transformation of the financial framework (increase of interest rates), the readily planned and permitted development could not be realised and the consortium partner ecovillage hannover was terminated. It is proposed in an on-going amendment process that the partner Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB) from the federal state of Brandenburg replaces ecovillage hannover as a member of the German pilot region. KWB will be collecting 100 m³/yr liquid human waste from the metropolitan region of Berlin for treatment applying the VN system in Eberswalde and thereby utilizing already established infrastructure. The liquid human waste will be collected from several urban events in and 24 public toilets in Berlin. Within P2Green, the existing VN treatment plant for the collected urine will be complemented by a distiller, so that the bio-based and certified fertiliser Aurin[®] can be produced. The installation of the distiller at KWB is planned by VN in the 3rd quarter of 2024. VN will also take care of necessary adjustments, operation and maintenance of the system as well as the fertiliser marketing. Goldeimer has collected dry toilet contents from festivals, allotment gardens and off-grid nature tourism destinations in the 2023 season. A thermophilic container-based composting plant for faeces is set up and operated by Goldeimer on the Vagtshoff farm in lower saxony near Hamburg to process them. The Vagtshoff farmer provides agricultural area (6 ha) for fertiliser application. Both faecal compost (~40 t[dm]) and Aurin[®] fertilisers (9,5 m³/yr) are yet used to grow agricultural crops. The field trial has been registered with the local authority.

The Spanish pilot region of La Axarquia: Bioazul has installed a water reclamation plant to treat and transform municipal wastewater from the wastewater treatment plant of Algarrobo into nutrient-optimised irrigation water for customised agricultural application. TROPS is yet applying the product to avocado and mango plots (120 trees total) in an optimised way, to be supported by a Smart Fertigation Tool, technology under development by AgriSmart Data. The refinement by the smart addition of nutrients, tailored to the nutritional demand of the specific crop, is in focus. It is key added value for producers to mainstream the reuse of wastewater resources for crop fertigation.

1 Background

In this chapter, the nexus of the state of the art of human sanitary waste management and geochemical flows such as nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P) is described as the given framework under which the three pilot regions operate. The maturation of P2Green's innovations in the pilot regions is contextualised with the current trends of sanitation systems, N & P nutrient flows and agronomy.

1.1 Detachment of the nutrient circles in the 20th century

In Paris, half of the city's urine was recycled and made use of only a century ago (Esculier & Barles, 2020; Ferguson, 2014). However, with the improvement of many country's wastewater treatment facilities in the mid-1900s, the recycling of human excreta subsided (Esculier & Barles, 2020). There was also growing awareness about the connection between poor sanitary hygiene and the spread of diseases. A parallel development was the industrial production of mineral fertilisers ("green revolution"), where both trends combined effected a transformation of the sanitary system into a linear system. As a result, less and less resources from wastewater were reclaimed (Mårald, 2000; Spink, 1979). In 2021, over 80 % of Europe's urban waste waters were collected and treated in line with EU legislation, which means that a daily total of 108.85 million m³ of wastewater is collected by sewer-based sanitation systems and treated in one of the >20,000 municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) across the EU.

When it comes to wastewater treatment in the EU, recent estimates show that 95% of urban wastewater is collected, 88% undergoes secondary (biological) treatment and 86% undergoes further treatment where nitrogen and phosphorus is partially removed (European Commission, 2022). A WWTP deposits the nutrients found in wastewater by releasing nitrogen back into the atmosphere and extracting the phosphorus as well as other nutrients as excessive sewage sludge, which is disposed via different methods depending on the regional context (cf. **Figure 2**). No municipal wastewater treatment plant is 100% efficient in their removal of nutrients (Pistocchi et al., 2023). Additionally, the use of water as a transport media for the operation of flushing toilets and sewer systems, without water reuse, relocates regional freshwater resources to the oceans.

Figure 1. The 2023 update to the nine key planetary boundaries, of which biogeochemical N- & P-flows as well as novel entities and freshwater change have transgressed the safe operating space. Licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 3.0. Azote for Stockholm Resilience Centre, based on analysis in Richardson et al 2023.

Developing a circular economy focused on recycling plant nutrients in the form of human excreta back to agricultural fields would reduce the current dependence on fertilisers derived from non-renewable resources (Ramírez & Worrell, 2006). It could also improve crop yields, for example in sub-Saharan Africa where fertiliser application is low (FAO, 2015), and protect marine ecosystems in many places by limiting the flow of excess nutrients to surface waters (Steffen et al., 2015).

With large amounts of water, also large amounts of nutrients and novel entities pass the WWTP and with its effluent are drained from cities to water bodies. Thereby the sanitation system contributes to exceeded planetary boundaries such as freshwater use, novel entities, biogeochemical N- & P-flows and climate change (cf. **Figure 1**). So called “death zones” - hypoxia areas of the oceans caused by eutrophication - play a significant role in the release of nitrous oxide (N₂O). The N₂O-production can be 10,000 times more than normally for sea water. This affects around 10 % of the water volume worldwide. Increasing death zones are resulting in increasing N₂O -emissions (Codispoti 2010), a greenhouse gas 297 times more potent than CO₂. In the Baltic Sea,

for example, the death zones grew in the last 110 years from 5,000 to 60,000 km² (Carstensen et al. 2014).

The growing concern about the future availability of fertilisers has highlighted the need for reclaiming the nutrients that exist in our sanitation system (Harder et al., 2019). Like today's linear economy, big proportions of fertiliser flows follow a linear pattern where extreme amounts of nutrients are simply leaked into the environment (Chojnacka et al., 2020). However, recovering nutrients derived from wastewater and human excreta could advance the European "Farm to Fork" strategy, linking increasingly urban populations to rural agricultural land (Trimmer & Guest, 2018). A circular nutrient economy entails ensuring high recovery rates of nutrients and biomass from human waste, such as human excreta and food waste, and recirculating it back to agriculture (Harder et al., 2019). This would significantly reduce the need for synthetic fertilisers (Hammer & Clemens, 2007), which require large amounts of fossil fuels to be manufactured (Glibert et al., 2014).

Raw materials to produce synthetic fertilisers are also being extracted at rates that are depleting global resources, such as in the case of phosphorus which is extracted from mining (Reijnders, 2014), whereas nitrogen is extracted from the atmosphere through the Haber-Bosch method (Menegat et al., 2022; Steffen et al., 2015). In 2022, global fertiliser demand reached almost 200 million metric tons, 110,8 of which was nitrogen, 50 was phosphorus and 39,1 was potassium (Statista, 2023a). Excessive or inefficient use of fertilisers lead to nutrient accumulation in water bodies, fostering primary biomass production (Jansson et al., 2019). This ends up depleting oxygen reserves, causing eutrophication which is devastating for marine life (Jansson et al., 2019). Despite already having breached the planetary boundary of biogeochemical flows, mainly due to our excessive use of fertilisers (Steffen et al., 2015), the global fertiliser demand is expected to increase to 208,3 million tons in 2026 (Statista, 2023b).

In the EU27, mineral fertilisers and manure make up >80 % of the nutrient sources for agriculture (cf. **Figure 2**). Animal manure production ranges above 1.4 billion tonnes of manure produced annually, of which >90% is directly applied to soils as fertiliser (Köninger et al., 2021). To achieve the European Commission's goals as declared in the European Green Deal (and its ancillary components such as the Farm to Fork Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan), both fertiliser types must be reduced in production and application rates. In organic farming, organic animal manure is the main source of nutrients. However, the market share of organic meat is low (3.9% organic meat 2022). There is a lack of authorised nutrient sources for crop and fodder production (sewage sludge excluded due to contaminants) and it is therefore crucial to explore further local, sustainable and safe sources of nutrients.

Figure 2. Relative distribution of N per pathway in the member states (Eurostat, 2020)

1.2 N- & P- emissions from current linear systems

Between 2005–2012, the nutrient load to European seas was 3,300–4,100 kt N/y of nitrogen and 260–300 kt P/y of phosphorus (Grizzetti et al., 2021). The majority of these are derived from mineral and manure fertilisers (71% N and 93% P). Together with atmospheric depositions (17% N), these can be considered the major diffuse inputs from human activities, whereas industrial and domestic waste waters (3,5% N and 5% P) are the major point pollution contributors to the accumulation of nutrients in European waters. The European Zero Pollution Action Plan targets to deliver a ‘near-zero water discharge’ of pollutants.

The numbers of nutrients discharged from WWTP vary greatly between countries. In Sweden, total nitrogen emissions amount to 51 kt N/y (Naturvårdsverket, 2021). Simultaneously, 33% of the nitrogen load and 16% of the phosphorus load Sweden emits to the Baltic Sea is derived from municipal wastewater effluent (Jordbruksverket, 2022). In Spain, WWTPs receive approximately 67 kt N/y, out of which 73% (49 kt N/y) is discharged into water bodies with the wastewater treatment plants effluent (Mayor et al., 2023). In Germany, thanks to wide application of tertiary treatment, the effluent contains only 19 % of the received N, but the specific annual per capita load of N discharged annually is comparable to that of Spain (cf. **Table 1**).

Table 1. Nitrogen release data for each pilot regions country

Pilot region / parameter	Annual N release total [kt N / y]	Annual N release specific [kg N / capita•y]	Annual N release to water bodies [kt N / y]	Share of agriculture (of N release to water bodies) [%]	Share of wastewater (of N release to water bodies) [%]	N from wastewater cumulated [kt N]
Sweden	51	5.0	15	47 %	33 %	13.7
Germany	1,547	18.3	585	79 %	14 %	106.0
Spain	913	18.8	779	93 %	6 %	47.0

Data from SRU, 2015; Tuholske et al 2021; Naturvårdsverket, 2021; Jordbruksverket, 2022; Mayor et al., 2023

The cumulative burden of Germany and Spain is significantly higher than that of Sweden. In an international study of global total nitrogen input via wastewater (6.2 Tg N) by Tuholske et al., 2021, Germany (#10) and Spain (#19) are ranged both in World's Top 20 (cf. **Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Germany (#10) and Spain (#19) are both in the Top 20 of global cumulative total nitrogen input via wastewater (6.2 Tg N) (Tuholske et al. 2021).

1.3 Contaminants contained in wastewater

With the heterogeneity of substances discharged from industry, hospitals, households and road run-offs, wastewater contains a diluted blend of such which are hazardous to human and the environment. A wider range of critical substances such as PFA's,, Microplastics or Heavy Metals is not or only in insignificant amounts excreted by humans (Sadia, Mahmood, Ibrahim et al., 2022; Forsberg, 2022; Larsen, Lienert, Udert, 2013). Heavy Metals are less of a concern in urine-derived fertilisers, than fertilisers derived from animal manure and conventional mineral fertilisers (Jönsson 2011). Heavy metal concentrations found in human urine are far below the Swedish limit for land application (Jönsson et al., 1997) and well below the levels in other biologically derived fertilisers (Hammer & Clemens, 2007; Jönsson et al., 2004).

Human solid waste contains hazardous pathogens. Pathogens are potentially also found in urine, mainly from faecal cross contamination; however, the produced urine fertiliser can be used directly as any potential pathogens are eliminated due to the harsh environment (pH, low water content and heat) (Senecal et al., 2022).

Pharmaceutical residues are frequently discussed when considering fertilisers derived from human excreta but are already a problem with lack of adequate sanitation and with conventional WWTPs. Pharmaceutical residues occur in very small concentrations in wastewater, and they are difficult to detect and remove at WWTPs (Luo et al., 2014), which are usually designed to treat bulk substances (Larsen et al., 2004). After passing through the WWTP, pharmaceutical residues remain biochemically active in water and can alter the behaviour of aquatic animals (Van Donk et al., 2016; Brodin et al., 2013).

If instead the pharmaceuticals are applied to land (via re-use of excreta as a fertiliser), then we would ingest fewer compounds, compared to what we ingest via the drinking water today. A simulation study in Levén et al. (2016) found that one would have to eat carrots or potatoes every single day for over 5 000 years to get one dose of the most resilient pharmaceutical compounds (over 20 000 years for the less resilient). The same simulation study found that intake of pharmaceutical residues would be at least 10-fold higher through drinking tap water in Stockholm (Levén, 2016). According to Vinnerås et al. (2008), several pharmaceutical substances are found in higher concentrations in animal manure compared to what can be expected in human urine. Overall, residual pharmaceuticals remaining in the fertiliser derived from human excreta are too low of a concentration to be of a risk to humans. Saying that, there is still an uncertainty about the risk to the micro-biome of the soil.

1.4 Sewage sludge management

From the total amount of approximately 40 billion m³ of wastewater treated in the EU annually, approximately 10 million tonnes of sludge (DM) derive.

The cases of Germany and Sweden are special. In 1999, the Federation of Swedish Farmers (LRF) recommended that their members stop using sludge because of concerns about its quality, a recommendation that many farmers still follow to this day. A study by Wallenberg & Eksvärd (2018) found that 85% of Swedish farmers who are offered to use sludge decline, mainly due to worries about traces of hazardous substances in the sludge. Despite this, Sweden's use of sludge has increased in recent years and in 2020, 34% of treated sewage sludge was recirculated back to agricultural land (SOU, 2020). This is largely thanks to the work of a WWTP certification called Revaq which strictly limits the number of pathogens and heavy metals that sludge can contain to be allowed as a fertiliser (Eurofins, n.d.). However, Revaq-certified sludge is only permitted for use in conventional farming (SOU, 2020).

In Germany, the novelation of the sewage sludge ordinance (AbfKlärV, 2017) limits the field application of sewage sludge significantly. By the year 2029 (> 100 kP.E.) and by 2032 (>50 kP.E.) respectively, treatment plant operators are obliged to recover phosphorous from sewage sludge. As the field application can in most cases not be matched with the new thresholds on pollutants, the mainstream path taken is the mono-incineration of sewage sludge whilst only a small number of municipalities is exploring the struvite path (cf. Project "Phosphor-Recycling in the heathlands and the Harz mountains", <https://p-net.tech>). Exceptions to the obligation to recover P only exist for sewage sludge with low phosphorus concentrations (less than 20 g P per kg of sewage sludge (dry matter)).

How sludge is treated across Europe also varies greatly from country to country. Whilst Germany incinerates most of its sludge already today, Spain and Sweden are mainly applying it to land (cf. **Figure 4**). Looking at field application, improvements in management and application are needed to reduce the large amounts of nutrient losses through gas emissions, leaching and runoff.

In the past, high levels of heavy metals in sludge for agricultural use were an issue in terms of its negative impacts on both soil and human health. Even though these levels have decreased up to 10 times within the EU, partly due to the EU's Sewage Sludge Directive: Council Directive 86/278/EEC, heavy metals in sludge still pose a threat to our food system (European Commission, 2023c).

Disposal of sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment by method of disposal, 2020
(% of total)

Note: Denmark, France, Italy, Portugal, Iceland, Switzerland, United Kingdom: no data or no recent data available

(1) Data for 2018 instead of 2020

(2) Data for 2019 instead of 2020

(3) Data estimated

(4) Data for incineration and other disposal are provisional

Source: Eurostat (online data code: env_ww_spd)

Figure 4. Disposal of sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment by method of disposal in % of total (Eurostat, 2020).

1.5 Transformation approaches - from disposal to reclamation

With the sanitation system evolved over the past 170 years in the global north, problems of public health have been tackled effectively. Sanitation has quickly transformed to a water system and thereby has been decoupled from the nutrition system. For most municipalities in Europe, the sewage system incorporates the largest scale infrastructures which are constantly growing with every household connected and every treatment step added to the WWTP and sludge management. But the system lock-in is not only manifested in concrete infrastructures, but also in the mind of the user, as with the water closet the comfort and peace of mind for people has improved significantly.

Hence a transformation of the sanitation system to become sustainable needs to address these barriers and to provide answers how the existing system can be transformed.

The main drivers for a sanitation transformation in Europe are ecological, whereas globally the tier of sanitation justice must be added. For most societies in the world, the aspects of nutrient and water stress resilience are becoming relevant factors whilst access to sanitation remains limited and SDG 6 remains behind its ambitions (WHO and UNICEF, 2020).

The P2Green solutions lever on various of these drivers. Advanced treatment for water reuse builds upon the lock-in of the water system and combines the reduction of emissions with resource reclamation for application as vital fertilisers for agricultural production.

Source separation provides system components that can be applied in various ways, from decentral to central it can be combined with the benefits of the sewer system whilst offering relief to it in terms of the needs for circular economy.

Source separation

In terms of toilets, source separation refers to the separation of human excreta as it enters the toilet. Therefore, the two very different compounds urine and faeces can be treated separately and in a more targeted manner. This is often implemented by using redesigned toilets or toilet attachments, such as urine diverting toilets. The separated urine can then be collected and treated separately, as it contains the largest proportion of valuable nutrients in our excreta, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, which have agronomic value (Simha et al., 2020b). Urine also contains the largest proportion of pharmaceuticals excreted (Lienert et al., 2007). Faeces also contains valuable nutrients and especially organic carbon which is also important for plant growth (Yadav et al., 2010). Faeces can be treated using various technologies, including composting toilets and anaerobic digesters, which can convert this organic mass into usable resources like compost, biochar, sludge fertiliser and biogas.

Nutrient recovery is one of the primary advantages of source separation as it offloads conventional WWTPs receiving a wastewater that is in better balance of nitrogen and carbon for an efficient biological process. At the WWTP, nitrogen removal is the most space and energy consuming activity of the entire treatment process (Beckinghausen et al., 2020).

Water reuse

The regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse (EU) 2020/741 shall be applied from 26 June 2023 on. Of the above mentioned 40 billion m³ of treated urban wastewater, only 1 billion m³ is being reused annually which constitutes a mere 2,5% (Water Reuse Europe, 2020). Spain is one of the largest wastewater producers in Europe, annually producing 5,68 billion m³. However, Spain is also one of the countries in the EU that reuses most of its wastewater (10-13%) (Jodar-Abellan et al., 2019). In

tandem, Germany annually produces 3,24 billion m³ of municipal wastewater and Sweden produces 1,18 billion m³ (Statista, 2023a).

In relation to the global market for water reuse solutions, there is a very interesting review of the sector performed in 2017 by the Water Reuse Europe (cf. **Figure 5**), with 787 schemes practicing reuse identified in the EU, distributed across 16 countries. Overall, agricultural reuse remains the most common water reuse application in Europe (with 39% of the schemes) followed by industrial reuse (15%) and reuse for recreational purposes (11%) (Water Reuse Europe, 2020).

Figure 5. Water reuse schemes per sector in Europe (Water Reuse Europe, 2020)

With the recent implementation of the Water Reuse Regulation, the Member States have been preparing for the application of the new rules, with many of them choosing to integrate the new rules into relevant national law or strategies. Some are also regulating water reuse for applications beyond agricultural irrigation.

Where treated wastewater is reused for irrigation in agriculture, this must be done in accordance with the new rules. However, the Water Reuse Regulation also allows Member States to decide not to practice water reuse in their territory or to limit the water reuse in certain areas. Some Member States, where freshwater resources are abundant and irrigation demand is low, have planned not to allow water reuse for irrigation in their countries. Some Member States have not yet made a final decision, as resource and infrastructure costs still are being evaluated. The **Figure 6** below shows which countries in the EU currently allow water reuse in agriculture.

Figure 6. Wastewater reuse allowance for agricultural irrigation in Member States (WISE, 2023).

2 Circular value chain description and maturation status

In this chapter, the maturation of the circular value chains is described per pilot region. The main organisational, technical, and legislative achievements and challenges are presented comprehensively and supplemented by the status and first results of the application of bio-based fertilisers in field trails and crop production. The main barriers identified are presented in one table per region and discussed.

Within the three pilot regions, there are four nutrient recycling approaches implemented. In Sweden, a pelletised fertiliser is generated from source separated urine, whilst in Germany the production of a liquid fertiliser is performed in parallel to the production of compost from human solid wastes. In the Spanish pilot region, the approach is based on the reuse of treated municipal wastewater as fertigation water customised to crop nutrient demands (cf. **Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Overview of the four different approaches and technology partners in P2GreenN.

In all three pilot regions, the planning for the implementation of each technology system is completed for re-connecting urban waste recovery with rural agri-food production, hence Milestone 1 of the project has been reached. The next steps towards the overall technology implementation to study the dynamic interfaces between rural/coastal and urban/industrial environments (Milestone 5) are described in chapter 3 Action plan.

2.1 Description and maturation of the Swedish circular value chain

In the Swedish Pilot, urine is collected, processed and used to grow barley which is brewed into beer. The technology to produce the solid urine fertiliser was developed at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) and Sanitation360 (S360), a spin-off from SLU started in 2019. To increase urine collection and to close the circular value, Touch Down (TD), local toilet rental company, and Gotlands Bryggeri, local beer brewer, joined to close the circular value chain. The aim in P2Green is to collect 150 m³ of urine by the end of the project to develop a dry fertiliser that can be used with conventional farming equipment. Currently, urine is collected in three hub locations in Sweden (Gotland, Uppsala and Malmö), with 6 m³ collected in 2023. Yet in 2024, over 11 m³ has been collected. During the coming 2,5 years, urine collection will be scaled-up within these hubs to reach to the goal. Urine collection can occur from both rural and urban areas and from public or private buildings depending on the installation. A large focus is also on developing methods for the removal of pharmaceuticals and other toxic substances in urine to be able to supply a quality-assured fertiliser. Therefore, tailoring the urine fertiliser we produce to farmers needs is also a major focus.

Maturity of the urinal rental value chain

The Swedish circular value chain starts with the production of a urine stabilizer which consists of a powdery, chemical compound marketed by S360 as Urmalullu™. Urmalullu™ is placed in the in-situ urine collection tank of urinals and urine diverting toilets. This compound stabilises the urea in the urine and prevents it from turning into ammonia, significantly reducing the occurrence of unattractive odours in and around the toilets as well as mitigating the loss the nitrogen as ammonia gas.

The urinals are supplied by the pilot region partner Touch Down, a local portable toilet service provider. The urine is collected and processed by S360 from urinals placed on the island of Gotland during peak tourist season. The urine is stored in airtight tanks that hold up to one cubic meter each. The urine is then dried, which increases the concentration of nitrogen from 0.6% to 15% and blended with a biological waste product to give it the right consistency for pellets to be made. The circular fertiliser is being evaluated by an independent third-party, Hushållningssällskapet, in field trials comparing dry-urine, liquid urine, commercial fertiliser (NKP: 24-4-5), and no fertiliser. In 2025/2026, the aim is to have produced enough fertiliser to work with subcontracted farmers in large-scale field trials (3-6 ha) with barley on Gotland. **Figure 8** showcases some of the process in photos.

Figure 8. Photos of urine recycling process on Gotland. From the left a) Touch Down urinals rented out on Gotland for events; b) urine-based granulars with NPK of 15-2-4; c) The urine-based fertiliser is used with conventional farming equipment to grow barley; d) Beer brewed from barley fertilized with urine based fertiliser

A local brewer and project partner, Gotlands Bryggeri, is using the harvested barley, fertilised with urine, for beer production. To date, there has been three beer tastings to ensure the quality of grain that is being produced reaches the demand of Gotland's Bryggeri. The aim is that by 2026, Gotland's Bryggeri will produce commercially available beer from barley fertilized with pelletized urine to close the value chain.

This closed circular value chain will be examined within the P2Green project and will be levered as proof of concept to show other food and beverage producers that S360's fertiliser is feasible, enabling a wider range of produce to be fertilized with urine.

The system will be installed and further optimized in a wider context at various locations on Gotland, using Touch Down's existing network and maintenance contracts. This includes public toilets in the city of Visby, public beaches and other new permanent installations. Expanding the production of urine-based fertiliser will enable integration into a circular value chain that can eventually move beyond Gotland and even Sweden.

Figure 9 below gives an overview of the flows of intellectual property, physical good and finances. Collection of urine at the other two hubs (Uppsala and Malmö) is performed with local portable toilet companies serving the respective cities and surrounding areas.

Figure 9. Scheme of the value circle of the Gotland pilot region. Note: The Production Facility is to be built in 2025.

Maturity of the safe urine fertiliser production process

At the start of the P2GreenN project, stabilised urine was being processed at about 60 L per day using primarily solar and wind energy. The limiting factor for increasing the treatment processing rate is access to sufficient urine and energy. Now, S360 has designed and invested in building a portable drying system that operates with waste heat from the local cement factory. The permission was received in November 2023 and the installation completed in May 2024, after the needed modifications at the cement factory had been implemented. The optimization of the system is on-going and is currently treating 21 L per m² per day. 250 L batches are reduced to 12 L which are then further processed into dried pellets. Concurrently, in the scope of national project RECAPTURE and interreg project CiNURGi and together with Soepenbergs Fertilisers BV, S360 is advancing in the pelletising of the urine fertiliser.

Figure 10. Installation of the urine drier that uses waste heat from cement production to concentrate the nutrients from urine by factor 25.

At SLU, several (other funded) projects investigating the removal of micro-pollutants during the drying process are carried out to determine that the cleanest fertiliser possible can be produced. The experiments are currently at bench-scale; however, existing technologies are being used, and adapted to urine, with the intention to be able to integrate the process before the end of this P2GreenN project. One study that evaluated the inactivation of 75 pharmaceuticals in urine showed that 90% of them were possible to reduce by 55% using UV light in the urine pre-drying (Demissie et al. 2023).

Maturity of field trials

Hushållningssällskapet (Rural Economy and Agricultural Societies, an independent agricultural advisor) is performing the barley field trials on Gotland with the dry urine fertiliser. The field trial in 2023 included 4 treatments: urine pellets, commercial fertiliser, liquid urine (unconcentrated) and no fertiliser. The equipment and field set-up are showcased in Figure 11. The farming equipment are replicates of conventional farming equipment, however, narrower so that it's possible to simulate using typically farming equipment without needing very large surface areas. A combi-seed drill is used to apply the fertiliser with the barley together directly into the soil. The width of the fertilized row is 1-2 cm and is placed 5-7 cm deep. The fertilized row is 6 cm from the seed row, like most combi-seed drills. Each replicate width is 1.5 m and 12 m long, and each treatment is replicated 6 times.

Figure 11. Farming equipment and set-up of field trials. From the left a) combi-seed drill where the barley and the urine pellets are buried into the soil 5-7 cm deep; b) visualisation of the 1.5 m wide replicates; and c) combine machinery used to harvest the barley grain.

In the 2022 field trial, the urine fertiliser was prilled, but this was too wet and the prills were not uniform and did not work well in the machine (nitrogen concentration achieved 7%). In winter 2023, SLU used a meat grinder to produce the pellets used for the summer 2023 field trials. The process worked; however, it was labour intensive and the quality varied (nitrogen concentration achieved 15%). In early 2024, SLU has worked with professional consultants in this field to assist with the production of granulars for this summer's 2024 field trials, which started in May 2024. The Hushållningsällskapet stated that the granulars would work well with conventional farming equipment as the granulars were uniform, firm and dried. However, the nitrogen concentration was 8%. The difference in the achieved nitrogen concentration is explained by (1) the source and quality of the urine. The higher concentration (15% nitrogen) was from urine collected from households, which contained the urine from all times of the day (the morning urine is the most concentrated with nutrients) and was collected in clean containers and remained stable overtime. The lower concentration (8% nitrogen) was from urine collected from festivals which has a lower nutrient content (more water) and more stabilizer was needed to maintain the pH as the urinals were not cleaned between uses. By working with Touch Down, a cleaning regiment will be implemented for 2024. In terms of the ideal nitrogen concentration, informal and formal discussions with farmers indicated that a minimum of 10% nitrogen concentration is needed to have a high acceptance rate by the farming community. Through collection of household urine and implementing a cleaning regime with Touch Down, this should be achieved in the 2024 urine collection.

The harvest from 2023 was the best thus far with 6 500 kg barley/ha harvested (extrapolated from the 6 replicates which were 1.5 m wide and 12 m long replicates) for both S360 fertiliser and the conventional fertiliser. The results are summarized in **Table 1**. The ideal protein content is between 9.5 and 11.5% for beer production. Higher protein values lead to inefficiencies in the brewing process and to increased foam (head) forming while serving the beer, which is less desirable. The higher protein values from 2023 harvest (13%, cf. **Table 2**) was investigated by SLU, S360 and Gotlands Bryggeri to help lower the concentration in the coming harvests. In short, it was a

general issue for malt barley producers in 2023 because of the dry start to the summer and the wet end of the summer.

Barley Field Trial 2023 Information

Planted: 2023-04-26 in Bro, Gotland Sweden by combi
Harvested: 2023-08-27
Barley Type: Planet
Surface area: 720 m² as depicted in the image on the left. The trial was in the middle of barley field seeded by the farmer Lars-Erik Westergren as seen in the image below.

Fertiliser Treatment	N-P-K Content (%)	Mass fertilizer applied (kg/ha)	P supplement (kg/ha)
S360 Fertilizer	15-2-4	567	29
NKP fertilizer	24-4-5	370	0
Fresh urine	0,6-0,07-0,2	14 167	21
Control	0-0-0	0	0

Figure 12. The Swedish Pilot 2023 Field trial information. The image on the left is the schematic of how the treatments were placed in the field as a randomised treatment block design. Note: the frass is from another fertiliser treatment experiment at SLU and the results are not reported here. The table above contains specific details about the fertilisers used. The image of the barley field showcases how the field trial was in the middle of the farmers own field of barley. All barley was irrigated as needed.

Table 2. Field trial results 2023

Fertiliser Type	Fertiliser Mass (applying 85 kg N/ha)	Yield (kg Barley/ha)	Protein (Ideal = 9.5 - 11%)
S360 Fertiliser	598 kg	6,500	13.0 %
Chemical (NPK)	370 kg	6,500	13.1 %
Fresh Urine	14,182 kg	5,500	13.6 %
No Fertiliser	0 kg	4,500	2.0 %

Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the Swedish pilot

In Sweden, it is a favourable prerequisite that urine is not forbidden as a fertiliser. However, for the technology to scale-up, a new supply and service chain is needed to support this paradigm shift. In looking at what financial incentives there are at each part of the value chain, it can be concluded that in Sweden there is little to no financial incentive at this point (cf. **Table 3**).

Table 3. Identified challenges and barriers of the Swedish pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.

	Tech	Acceptance	Financial Incentive
Collection at source	Systems on the market; Development needed	Low use of urinals; high price UDDT	None to against
Treatment	In development (TRL 6)	Too many questions and unclear responsibility	Little to none
Reuse	Fertiliser = good; Final product in development	High acceptance with farmers; however, too small volumes	None

The acceptance of recycled nutrients from urine will likely remain relatively low because of the cost of the collection infrastructure, the treatment system and of producing the fertiliser. In addition, as the municipalities are mandated to provide sanitation services, there are many uncertainties in terms of accountability across the different actors of alternative sanitation value chains.

In terms of acceptance with the farmers, they have stated that the use of urine as a fertiliser is very welcome, however the current production volumes are too small (Parfitt, 2023). And within this P2GreenN work package (WP 1), the aim is to address the column

under technology in order to increase the amount of urine we are able to collect, treat and produce as a fertiliser, whilst other columns are tackled by colleagues from other WPs.

In addition, SLU investigated (2023-2024) the availability of the nitrogen from the urine fertiliser compared to mineral fertiliser produced by Yara (24-4-5). The incubation trial replicated field conditions over a span of 63 days and demonstrated that the urine pellets are a viable alternative to commercial NPK fertiliser. The urine pellets had comparable mineral N release dynamics. This supported the field trials (results above in **Table 2**) which showed significantly higher yields in urine fertilized barley compared to unfertilized soil, and the same yield to the NPK fertilized barley.

Governance readiness level for the Gotland Business Model

Even though Sweden has been a pioneer in developing resource-recovery sanitation solutions since the 1990s, implementation rates of these systems have been at a standstill for decades (Bengtsson & Tillman, 2004; Söderholm et al., 2023). The expansion of installation was not followed by the necessary economic incentives to create a sanitation market (Johansson et al., 2009). In addition, the relatively small volumes of urine collected to be used as fertiliser made it uneconomical for farmers to invest in storage tanks etc. that is needed for reuse (Johansson et al., 2009).

The high water content of 95% in urine makes it comparably less efficient to collect, store, transport and apply it as a fertiliser (Senecal & Vinnerås, 2017; Johansson et al., 2009). This, along with Sweden's highly centralised wastewater treatment systems are just some examples of the existing technological lock-in barriers working against the scaling-up of nutrient recycling (Söderholm et al., 2023).

Revaq is the Swedish Water and Sewerage department's own quality insurance system for assuring the sludge quality. Revaq-certified WWTPs treat approximately half of Sweden's municipal wastewater and are built to remove nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus from the aqueous phase, for phosphorus with a focus on binding it to the sludge (Eurofins, n.d.). Whilst Revaq is a great circular initiative, this certification is not relevant for S360s urine fertiliser as it only covers sludge that is processed at WWTPs.

In addition, the governance framework creates uncertainty for source-separation systems. It arises from the absence of explicit definitions for urine, sludge, and wastewater in regulations, adding a layer of difficulty to their categorization.

Source-separated fractions, including urine, do not neatly align with existing regulations, such as the water and wastewater provision regulation (SFS 2006:412), the sludge regulation (SNFS 1994:2), or the waste management regulations (SFS 1998:808, SFS 1998:899, and SFS 1998:944). Particularly, the regulation restricting the use of plant nutrients in agriculture (SJVFS 2004:62), while explicitly regulating sludge, lacks mention of human urine. (M. Ahlström, personal communication, November 17th, 2023)

Compounding the complexity is the dual regulatory framework based on the location of wastewater generation. Wastewater within public water utilities service areas falls under one set of rules (SFS 2006:412), overseen by water utilities. In contrast, wastewater from private and communal facilities outside these service areas, notably in small rural communities, is subject to a different set of rules (SFS 1998:808, 20 §), with waste utilities taking responsibility. It must be emphasized that if collected outside public water utilities service areas, urine fractions are deemed waste rather than sludge, further contributing to the intricate legal considerations surrounding urine management in Sweden. (M. Ahlström, personal communication, November 17th, 2023)

In practice, urine is allowed for use in conventional farming in Sweden which enables S360's urine fertiliser to be used by conventional farmers and for them to be able to legally sell their produce. However, it used to be allowed in organic farming as well before Sweden joined the EU in 1994. Joining the EU meant that Sweden had to follow the EU's regulations for organic farming, which does not permit urine to be used as a fertiliser. In Sweden there is another common certification for sustainable farming called KRAV, which could become a potential certification for urine. However, in order to be a KRAV certified farmer in Sweden, the farmer first has to be certified EU-organic. These two certifications therefore go hand in hand and urine fertiliser is not mentioned as an option in KRAV's regulation under section 12.3 "fertilisers and soil improvement". This prohibits S360s urine fertiliser from being both EU-organic and/or KRAV certified.

Organic/KRAV-certified farming constitutes about 20% of farmed land in Sweden and out of the farmers S360 has talked to, the organic/KRAV farmers have also been those who've showed the greatest interest in using urine fertiliser (Parfitt 2023). The European legislative framework is a market inhibitor for the scaling-up urine-based fertilisers.

The national SPCR 178 certification is currently the only applicable fertiliser certification for source-separated urine. It might go out of commission due to the relatively high costs of obtaining and maintaining the certification. Furthermore, the circular and environmental benefits of choosing urine need to be added to the SPCR178 certification for S360 to see a value in obtaining it. On the legislation side SJVFS 2004:62 regulate the use of fertiliser on agricultural land. All organic fertilisers of biological origin are allowed for use in Swedish agriculture. The restrictions are on the amount applied, assuring not to over-fertilise, and related to wastewater products not to add high levels of heavy metals.

2.2 Description and maturation of the North German Plain circular value chain

The circular value chain of the pilot region in Germany (cf. **Figure 13**) consists of four partners and is based on an interregional urban-rural transaction and divisional treatment of solids and liquid human sanitary waste.

The partner ecovillage hannover (EVH) was terminated by December 15th 2023 and had to leave the consortium, because with the transformation of the financial framework the development had to be stopped. From that point on AGR took over the Co-Lead staff formerly contracted by EVH to secure the continuation of the all-over project.

With the on-going amendment process, EVH is anticipated to be substituted by new partner Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB), located in Brandenburg. The pilot region was therefore renamed from Hamburg-Hanover to North German Plain. In consequence, based the on-going amendment, the tasks and deliverables shown in **Table 10** will be impacted.

EVH was planning to collect approximately 100 m³/yr urine from 350 tenants using 100 urine diverting flush toilets (UDFT). The separated yellow water (urine + flushing water) was planned to be drained via a dedicated network serving an area of 2 ha. The urine was meant to be processed at the premises of EVH in a central facility using the Aurin[®] system provided by VunaNexus (VN).

KWB is a regional recycling hub serving approximately 200.000 citizens in the county of Barnim and, as a company (GmbH), is fully owned by the county. Since 2019, in partnership with the private company Finizio, they facilitate a back-end solution for public and event dry toilets for the Berlin metropolitan region, reclaiming solid human waste from urban events at the scale of >250.000 people per year. The Berlin city senate and the Barnim county government are operating permanent public dry toilets in urban spaces. In 2023, KWB implemented a liquid human waste (i.e. urine) treatment capacity of 100 m³/yr in cooperation with VN. This creates the possibility to adsorb micropollutants and to recover most nutrients from human excreta while reducing freshwater demand in urban areas. VN will take care of necessary adjustments, operation and maintenance of the system. The Aurin[®] fertiliser will be marketed by VN.

Goldeimer (GE) collects dry toilet contents from festivals, allotment gardens and off-grid nature tourism destinations. A three-staged container-based composting facility for faeces is operated by GE on the Vagtshoff farm in lower saxony near Hamburg producing a quality assessed compost. The Vagtshoff farm provides the agricultural fields for fertiliser application.

Both bio-based fertilisers (cf. **Figure 14**) are applied in a combined way within field trials at Vagtshoff to produce rye and barley.

Figure 13. Scheme of the value circle of the North German Plain pilot region.

Figure 14. The bio-based fertiliser products produced in the Pilot Region North German Plain are Aurin®, which is an authorised fertilising product in Austria, Switzerland, (left photo by Vuna GmbH – vuna.ch) and (right) KIT, a compost made from solid human waste from dry toilets (right photo by Finizio GmbH – finizio.de).

Maturity of EVH/KWB premises and VunaNexus treatment installations

With the beginning of the P2GreenN project, the planning of each of the 15 houses of the first construction sector had been finished, including the new toilet types, the additional piping and specific venting and maintenance requirements. The planning for the yellow water network as well as the flushing water distribution (from treated greywater), has been developed from a level of basic determination to a design planning status. Knowledge exchange with the St. Vincent de Paul project engineers from Paris, where the network has already been implemented in 2021, has been initialised. Due to the transformation of the financial framework (sudden increase of interest rate) it has not been matured further from this point on.

Figure 15. Images and schemes of the urine diverting flush toilet (UDFT) planned for EVH (above, courtesy of EOOS NEXT) and one urine diverting dry toilet (UDDT) type used by KWB subcontractor (below, courtesy of Finizio)

The development of 160 flats for approx. 350 people was ready to be executed: The property plot had been purchased, the planning had been completed, the building for the 15 planned houses had been permitted.

A first demonstration building has been built ('Modulpilot'), where the execution has been successfully taken place on the building scale level. Based on the commercial UDFT "save!" from manufacturer Laufen (cf. **Figure 15** above), questions of the piping (dimensions, angles, shaft allocation), maintenance access have been tackled and as well as the capacity building of the installation company has taken place based on a newly developed yellowwater planning and installation guideline elaborated by aquaplaner engineers. The insights have been shared with the regional project salesperson of the save! toilet manufacturer Laufen Roca for dissemination.

KWB is contracting Finizio with the collection of liquid human waste and transporting it to KWB for treatment by the VN system in Eberswalde and thereby utilizing already established infrastructure (cf. **Figure 16**). The liquid human waste will be collected from several urban events in Berlin and 24 public toilets which Finizio is operating in Berlin. The distance between Berlin and Eberswalde is 50 km.

Within P2GreenN, the existing VN treatment plant for the collected urine will be complemented by a distiller and operated at the KWB site. The VN system consists of

three treatment steps, of which two have been installed and tested at KWB via the national funded project “zirkulierBAR” in 2023 to demonstrate the urine stabilisation and filtration process. But only with the final treatment step of volume and pathogen reduction through the distiller, the bio-based and certified fertiliser Aurin® can be produced. The installation of the distiller at KWB is planned by VN in the 3rd quarter of 2024. This will give VN the possibility to further scale-up and optimise their Aurin® production technology (described above) in a challenging context as the installation at KWB is a container-based technical installation whilst so far, the certified fertiliser Aurin® is being produced from installations in buildings. Due to the more exposed environment as well as the different composition of the raw material from UDDTs, the container must be enhanced to counterbalance the exposure to variability in temperature. Moreover, the automation (hardware and software) is being adapted to this containerised system. All of this in order to reach an increase from TRL 6 to TRL 8. The container-based approach could increase the potential market for the VN technology as well as its scalability.

Figure 16. Container-based VunaNexus urine treatment system at KWB premises

Maturity of Vagtshoff premises and Goldeimer treatment installations

At the Vagtshoff farm in the municipality Hanstedt, GE has been operating its material and logistics hub since the year 2015. GE’s value proposition is to make a walk to the loo a fun experience on public events, to educate people on resource-oriented sanitation and the global sanitation crisis (SDG 6). Since 2013 they are providing their 80 mobile toilets (cf. **Figure 17**, left) mainly to music festivals.

Figure 17. Event toilets as provided by project partner Goldeimer and bins used for solid waste logistics.

But until today, GE was not able to comply with its intention to close the value chain from excretion to nutrition from their own capabilities. Collected faeces have been treated at Germany's so far only recycling premise for human excreta collected without water in Eberswalde, operated by the network partner Finizio. The process consists of three treatment steps:

1. Sanitisation of dry toilet contents by thermophilic composting
2. De- & Recomposition of organic matter by oxygen-controlled composting
3. Extraneous material extraction by screening

Based on the experiences of Finizio (TRL 5), the GE composting system aims at improving economic viability with the introduction of a new technology for the oxygen-controlled composting (Step 2). The highly automated and so called "earthflow" composting system is displacing Finizios labour intense heap process, whereas the first step of the process is adapted without substantial modifications. Therewith, both steps 1 and 2 can be facilitated container-based.

Figure 18. 3-D image of the “Earthflow” container for highly automated and oxygen-controlled faeces composting at Vagtshoff (courtesy of Green Mountain Technologies)

The machinery has been purchased and installed at the Vagtshoff (cf. **Figure 19**). The Earthflow container was put into test operation under local and remote operation modes.

As usual for composting plants, Vagtshoff is obliged to operate on hydraulically sealed surface. In April 2024, the building permission was granted by the local construction authority, with the involvement of the public authorities of water, emissions, waste and nature conservation.

Figure 19. Top – Container system for the sanitisation of dry toilet contents by thermophilic composting (step 1). Bottom: “Earthflow” container system for De- & Recomposition of organic waste by oxygen-controlled composting (step 2). Aeration pipes are covered by composting fleece and wood chips. Followed by biomass to be de- & recompositioned

With the support of LEADER fundings, Goldeimers sister company PyCCS GmbH has commissioned a pyrolysis plant at the Vagtshoff. The goal is to produce biochar as a) litter supplement for the operation of dry toilets (“dry flush” to cover faeces and adsorb odor) and b) to improve the physico-chemical properties of the faecal compost receiving soils by addition of biochar in the composting process in the Earthflow container.

Maturity of field trials at Vagtshoff

Both faecal compost (~40 t DM) and Aurin® (9,5 m³/yr) fertilisers are used to grow agricultural crops. The test area is located in the municipality Hanstedt on the coordinates 53 ° 13,52.0 "N 10 00'36.9" E in a water protection zone. The sandy soils have been extensively used in recent years without adding fertilisers. A total area of 6 ha was planned to be used for the field test (cf. **Figure 20**).

The recycling fertiliser from faecal compost (KIT: Kompost aus Inhalten von Trockentoiletten = compost from dry toilet contents) and Aurin® are planned to be applied on an area of 4.56 ha. This roughly corresponds to the area that is needed in order to be able to spend the quantities of recycling fertilisers (faecal compost + Aurin®) produced during the project duration. The planned output of faecal compost is well below the upper limit for compost fertilisers (30 t DM/ha in three years) defined in the BioAbfV § 6. The limits of the output quantities of faecal compost and Aurin® are therefore largely resulting from the N and P requirements of the plants. The rest of the area is required for the comparison treatments (0.48 ha) and a not fertilized edge strip of at least 9 m to the next blow (0.96 ha).

KIT is integrated into the soil shortly before seeding, whereas Aurin is applied before seeding as well as shortly before both fruit formation and bolting.

Figure 20. Top: Structure of the field trial near Hamburg with the arrangement of the measuring plots for various fertiliser treatments in a "Latin Square Design". Bottom: Field trails 3 weeks after seeding of summer rye. Perspective: eastwards, photo taken on 13.5.2024

The concept has been registered and acknowledged based on DüMV §4 4/5 by the federal fertiliser authority, with the exclusion of realising the r0 area (4.56 ha). As this limitation is missing a comprehensive justification from the authority, the partners of the pilot region are planning to claim the full scope for subsequent field trials.

Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the German pilot

The main challenges for the German pilot region originate in the legislative framework (cf. 3.2.5). The intersectoral, unclear legislation and the locally diverting and arbitrary decision making have impacts on the technical planning. Authorities have the duty to avoid risk for people, animals and the environment, and where the risk has not been

clarified by law or technical directives, the legal and administrative requirements to safeguard all risk prevention measures are often system overarching whilst public administration is often limited to their pre-determined scope of singular (and linear) responsibility. Two examples shall provide more specific details on the described situation.

Regarding the yellowwater network for evh, the interaction with the local authority (Stadtentwässerung Hannover) showed that the requirements for domestic discharge waters (SEH, 2016) limit the interaction of the yellow water and the sewer system. For the potential occurrence of yellow water system overflow, the sewer system offers capacities. But the high nutrient content of yellow water is well above the existing parameter thresholds for discharge and therefore has a strong impact on the technical requirements as well as the effort to monitor the system. To cope with this challenge technically, an additional tank to dilute yellow water overflow with greywater discharge was foreseen, but naturally has a negative economic impact. It remains unclarified if more cost-effective governance solutions could have been achieved.

Barriers for the yellow water collection also exist based on the currently higher prices of the innovative user interfaces (UDFT).

Event toilets are typically rented by the event owner. Urine Dry Diverting Toilets (UDDT) for use as event toilets must be serviced closely to guarantee user acceptance and thereby result in higher fees compared to conventional chemical mobile toilets. UDDTs for use as public toilet typically require significantly less investment costs due to the unnecessary of establishing sewer and drinking water connections.

Regarding the treatment, the technology itself is ready to be demonstrated in operational environment, but its price and area footprint result in additional costs for owners or tenants. As the product Aurin® cannot yet be marketed locally, hence the nutrient reclamation is hindered and the financial incentive for the implementation of the closed value chain is not given. The challenges and barriers for human waste reclamation in the German pilot are aggregated in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Identified challenges and barriers for urine valuation in the North German plain pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.

	Tech	Acceptance	Financial Incentive
Collection at source	Validated logistic chain	Broad acceptance by users	higher cost than conventional
Treatment	VunaNexus container integration requires further optimization	technologies close to common wastewater standards	Treatment cost higher than deposit to sewer
Reuse	Product recognized in partner country, open questions of farming applicability	General openness by farmers, but illegal	Price of mineral fertilisers lower; no benefit from eco-engagement

In terms of the faecal composting, the water draining from the grounds which are used as material hub is believed to be considered contaminated and harmful for humans and environment by the local authorities and as such must be captured, stored and eventually deposited in a controlled manner. This requires advanced constructive works and spendings on a drainage system, logistics and deposition fees. The additional costs originating from this requirement might be a crucial barrier for follower farmers to take up this business opportunity. Goldeimer investigates the actual risks of harmful leakages from the containerized systems.

In terms of the faecal composting, the subjective barriers aggregated in **Table 5** also turn out to be challenging. Whilst the technological readiness level and the acceptance in terms of material collection and treatment is not recognized as a barrier, the financial incentives and the feasibility of the product application and thereby the valuation of the closed faeces value chain is hindered by the current legislative framework.

Table 5. Identified challenges and barriers for faeces valuation in the German pilot region rated by their perceived level: red = higher; orange = medium; and green = lower barrier.

	Tech	Acceptance	Financial Incentive
Collection at source	Operated; amounts sufficient	Public awareness rising	higher cost than conventional
Treatment	Technology ready, optimisation ongoing	Similar to other farmers practices	Treatment cost higher than conv. composting
Reuse	Only within research framework	General openness by farmers, but illegal	no incentive for regenerative agriculture

Governance readiness level of the North German Plain value chain

In Germany, the P2Green project encounters a plethora of legislative barriers. Challenges span from waste transformation compliance to setting up decentralized systems. Legal complexities impact yellow water and urine collection and treatment, faecal composting, and field trials. However, potential opportunities arise from aspired federal living-lab laws.

The main entry barriers for the P2Green products are to comply legally and to assure its harmlessness. But also on the way of transformation from waste to resource qualified to become a produce, various barriers exist in different sectors and laws. Whereas yellow water collected from less than 50.000 PE appears to be qualified for N- and P-recycling as sewage sludge in accordance with the CMC regulation, this is not the case for contents of dry toilets as they are confronted with barriers in the municipal statutes based on the Water Household Act (WHG §55/56), the Circular Economy Act (BioAbfV §3) and the Fertiliser Act (DüMV Annex II, Table 7). There is also no guidance for the waste key application to sanitary waste from dry toilets (91/689/EEC; AVV). This fundamentally counteracts the principle of the waste hierarchy – Prevent, Reuse, Recycle, Recover, Dispose - of the federal Circular Economy Act (KrWG § 6 (1)).

EVH planning guidelines for yellow water integration into buildings are published and distributed throughout stakeholders (architects, building technical equipment planning). The planning of the district-wide yellow water collection system is at the state of a design planning and has not matured further.

Due to the above-mentioned delays, the engineering of the decentral wastewater system of EVH has not been finished. Nevertheless, in terms of yellow water, insights into the Water Household Act and its subordinated rules have been made multiple (cf. above). The overall path pursued technologically and legislatively in Germany for sanitary waste is strictly encompassing sanitary waste as wastewater. The renewed sewage sludge regulation (AbfKlärV 2017) and its Governance Framework is streamlining stakeholders to the mono-incineration of sewage sludge with the aim of P-reclamation from ashes. The soil-regenerating- and N-potentials of sanitary waste are fully compromised on this pathway.

Regarding the set-up of the faecal matter composting, a building permission path according to building regulations of Lower Saxony under consideration of agricultural privilege has been followed.

The area falls under the AwSV and the TRwS 792 / JGS rules with less requirements and evidence obligations than for clients outside agronomy. This agricultural privilege has been identified as a high-potential entry point in the development of business models for farmers. However, the consultation of an AwSV expert has been ordered by the authorities and states an additional barrier.

Currently there is a stalemate regarding the accountability for the drainage water from the faeces composting facility: Agricultural wastewater may not be fed into the public wastewater disposal system of the district or municipality. At the same time, the wastewater produced during the composting of human excreta may not be used for regular agricultural purposes as liquid manure without special permission from the fertiliser authorities. The next step will be to seek clarification with both public authorities once the planned constructions are permitted.

With the building permission, the operation of the composting facility with human waste as a side stream is authorized for a time span of three years under the umbrella of the innovation project P2Green.

The field trials can only be legally performed based on the privilege of scientific projects and on the experimental paragraph of the German fertiliser Act (DüMV §4 4/5). The treatment of the sanitary waste is lacking existing jurisprudence, as human excreta is defined out of the ordinance for the treatment of organic waste (BioAbfV §3).

It has to be highlighted, that the fact that the field trial area is located in a water protection area did not play a role in the registration process.

In-depth studies on the option of achieving CE label for the studied bio-based fertilisers from human excreta are provided in deliverable D3.7 Scoping review describing the status of the legislative framework.

The only national framework that is promising to open new opportunities on this endeavour is a new living-lab law (Reallabore-Gesetz), which is currently under development in the Ministry of Economy.

2.3 Description and maturation of the Spanish circular value chain

The Spanish pilot is composed of five project partners, namely: AXARAGUA as the public operator of the Algarrobo municipal wastewater treatment plant, BIOAZUL as technology provider for wastewater reclamation, the farmers cooperative TROPS for the crop management and as technical advisor for fertigation, AgriSmart Data as software developer of the Smart Fertigation Tool and the water research centre CETAQUA as scientific partner for the analysis of the collected data.

The circular value chain of the Axarquía pilot region starts with the collection of sewage from the municipality of Algarrobo and nearby municipalities. The raw wastewater of this community is sourced exclusively from urban settlements, with no industrial wastewater discharged into the sewage system. Municipal wastewater is collected and transported to the Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) of Algarrobo (coordinates: 36°45'13.0"N, 4°02'55.8"W). The WWTP receives an average influent of 2.150 m³/day (i.e. 12.247 p.e.), with maximum capacity of 24.000 p.e.. It is operated and maintained by AXARAGUA, a public company created by the "Association of Municipalities of the Costa del Sol-Axarquía" to directly manage the drinking water and wastewater treatment of the joint municipalities. Besides Algarrobo, AXARAGUA carries out the wastewater treatment in the municipalities of Vélez-Málaga, Rincón de la Victoria, Torrox and Benamocarra.

The raw wastewater from the sewer system, once it enters the WWTP, goes through a series of primary and secondary filtration, sedimentation and flocculation procedures. The secondary treatment must offer optimal treatment performance, complying with the provisions of the European Directive 91/271/EEC. After the secondary treatment, the outflow is discharged entirely into the sea through an underwater outfall. As there is no denitrification process in place, the amount of nitrogen released from the Algarrobo WWTP to the mediterranean sea is relatively high (28,8 tN/year).

In the Spanish pilot region, a tertiary treatment (i.e., Water Reclamation Plant) is replacing the before existing RichWater® system installed in the proximity of the WWTP by BIOAZUL. The water reclamation plant is operating and providing reclaimed water in the scope of P2Green since Month 3 (February 2023). An approximate volume of 16 m³/day, tailored to suit the crops needs, of secondary effluent from the WWTP outlet is transported through a pump that feeds the tertiary system. After the tertiary treatment, the effluent is classified as reclaimed water, a nutrient-rich effluent with agronomic value. Reclaimed water is then transported through a pipeline and stored in a deposit tank, part of the mixing unit. From the deposit tank, reclaimed water will be used to fertigate the crops and, if needed, it will be supplemented by mineral fertilisers or diluted with local water, under the control of the Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT). The Water Reclamation Plant is operated by BIOAZUL the coordinator of the pilot region.

Reclaimed water will be used to fertigate avocado and mango crops planted outdoors in the test site. The crops are cultivated and managed by the pilot region partner TROPS, a cooperative of around 3,000 farmers in the region, but also technical and agronomic

advisor on crop management. Based on the crop demands, in terms of irrigation and nutrients, the fertigation is adjusted to meet the requirements of the trees.

In this sense, the Smart Fertigation Tool will provide information on the level of main nutrients and elements in the soil that most affect the development of crops. The tool allows the connection of sensors and transducers installed in the soil that will provide information on multiple parameters and can also manage irrigation and fertilisation automatically, based on the actual levels in the roots of the plants. The tool will also incorporate data from water sensors installed in the measurement tank with reclaimed water. Additionally, the tool will allow the remote control over the dosage of fertilisers and mixture of water sources automatically, by means of a Decision Support System (DSS) integrated. The Smart Fertigation Tool will indicate whether additional nutrients are necessary in the reclaimed water, incorporating mineral fertilisers, but also if there is a need to dilute the nutrient-rich effluent with local water (mainly groundwater). This smart fertigation prevents from excessive nutrient application and thereby mitigates the emission of polluting leachates into water bodies (N- and P-emissions to surface and groundwater). The SFT, will be developed by the partner AgriSmart Data, the software developer.

The agroecological and environmental impact assessment, as well as the validation of the data collected in the pilot (including analysis of local water, reclaimed water, soil, etc.) will be carried out by CETAQUA, a water research centre, in collaboration with partners from Work Package 2.

Figure 21. Scheme of the value circle of the Axarquía pilot region.

Maturity of water reclamation

The Water Reclamation Plant providing the tertiary treatment consist of three stages (cf. **Figure 22**):

- Discs filtration
- Ozone disinfection
- Maintenance disinfection

Figure 22. Flow diagram of tertiary treatment and disinfection

The treatment and production capacity of the Water Reclamation Plant is around 3,000 litres per hour of reclaimed water. The plant is currently running and operated 5.5 hours per day, meaning a potential daily production of up to 16.500 litres per day (16 m³/d of reclaimed water).

The tertiary filtration treatment aims to reduce the content of suspended solids and organic matter, guaranteeing the retention of harmful microorganisms and prepare the water to subsequently apply a disinfection treatment, achieving a suspended solids reduction of up to 80% (cf. **Figure 23**).

Figure 23. Raw wastewater entering the WWTP (left beaker), treated wastewater after secondary treatment in WWTP (middle beaker), and reclaimed water after tertiary treatment in water reclamation plant (right beaker)

Among the different existing technologies, the installation of a manually cleaned ring filter has been chosen, due to the low flow rate to be treated and the good performance it offers in the long-term, its smaller occupation surface and its lower operation and maintenance costs, simplifying these tasks.

These lower operation and maintenance costs are due to the fact that disc filters (cf. **Figure 24**) have a limited number of ducts, without air requirements for cleaning, with great simplicity of the control systems. They present an excellent response to increases in load. The degree of filtration to be used is set at 100 μm (100 microns).

Once the pressure set on the pressure switch is reached, the filter cleaning protocol will be activated. In our case the filter discs are cleaned manually, but automated backwash installations are also available. Once the washing process is completed, the hydrostatic pressure resistance is decreased, and the equipment filter performance is restored.

Figure 24. Discs filtration towers, control panel and pipeline towards mixing unit

In relation to the subsequent disinfection stage, the objective here is the destruction of pathogenic microorganisms through ozone (O_3) disinfection, it is automated and requested to comply with the EU Regulation 2020/741 on water reuse.

In addition, as the pilot includes the use of storage and regulation tanks, it is necessary to include a chlorination system (with NaClO dosage) to maintain the reclaimed water properties and avoid contamination and proliferation of algae and pathogenic organisms. As it is depicted in the flow diagram in **Figure 22**, the dosage of NaClO takes place before and after the disc filtration process. The reason to add NaClO before filtration is to prevent the potential growth of filamentous bacteria and subsequent blockage of the discs in the event that these microorganisms are present in secondary effluent from the municipal WWTP, which might hinder the effectiveness of this advanced treatment. A control of the free residual chlorine in the effluent is carried out and action levels can be established according to this control of free residual chlorine. In this way, the necessary dose is regulated to maintain its quality until the point of delivery for fertigation.

Once the reclaimed water is produced, it is transported through a pipe to a measurement tank located in a mixing station (next to the fields with avocado and mango crops), where continuous monitoring of various physicochemical parameters is carried out using probes that are connected to a Hach data logger, model SC-1000. The attached probes are measuring turbidity, temperature, pH, electrical conductivity, ammonium, potassium, nitrate, and chloride levels.

Figure 25. Measurement tank with reclaimed water (upper pic) and submerged probes in the measurement tank for continuous monitoring of various physicochemical parameters (bottom images)

The measuring tank is a transit place that is permanently filled with reclaimed water with the probes submerged. When the new influent arrives, the measurement is made and by gravity it is channeled into one storage tank designated for use in irrigation.

Figure 26. Data logger and mixing unit with storage tanks for well water and reclaimed water

As regulations require that there is no cross contamination due to mixing of different sources of water in the pipes, independent pipe systems are used for reclaimed water and conventional well water.

At this point, the high agronomic value of reclaimed water (produced by the Water Reclamation Plant) as a fertiliser in agriculture is recognised, as it is described next.

Building on the results reported in the previous version of this deliverable, **Table 6** includes the average content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium included in reclaimed water in comparison with local water used at the test site. The table includes the average value from May 2023 to November 2023 (7 months), and the updated average value until April 2024 (11 months), in line with the two versions of this deliverable.

Taking into account the period from May 2023 to April 2024, the average value of NPK content in reclaimed water is 36.56 mg N / l, 5.65 mg P / l and 31.78 mg K / l. With regards to local water, the average value of NPK content analysed in the same period is 12.69 mg N / l, 0.09 mg P / l and 2.63 mg K / l.

In a later stage of P2Green, we will be able to compare the NPK content of reclaimed and local water, with the final effluent adjusted by the Smart Irrigation Tool, containing the optimal amount of NPK, based on the crop needs.

Table 6. Comparison of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content between local water and reclaimed water in two different periods

	May 23 - November 23			May 23 - April 24		
	N-total (mg/l)	P-total (mg/l)	K-total (mg/l)	N-total (mg/l)	P-total (mg/l)	K-total (mg/l)
Reclaimed water	30	5.84	37.1	36.56	5.65	31.78
Local water	12.45	< 0.05	2.41	12.69	0.09	2.63

During the lifetime of the probes and sensors continuously monitoring physicochemical parameters in the measurement tank with reclaimed water, it is essential to run several calibration processes. In this sense, the probes that monitor turbidity, temperature, pH, electrical conductivity, ammonium, potassium, nitrate, and chloride levels were calibrated against samples analysed by an external laboratory in March 2024.

Maturity of field trials

For the field trials, a wide range of renovation and adaptation works were performed in the test site at the beginning of the P2Green project. This allowed the preparation and eventual use of two separated plots dedicated to avocado and mango crops.

Renovation works conducted include the removal of old greenhouse, assembling of new greenhouse, digging and exchange of soil, preparation of ridges, irrigation pipelines, etc. (cf. **Figure 27**).

Figure 27. Test site construction and adaptation works.

According to the experimental design and agronomic study, 60 avocado trees (Hass variety) and 60 mango trees (Osteen variety) were planted on an area of approximately 850 m².

In general, avocado crops are quite demanding for nitrogen in order to achieve an adequate growth and development of the plants, unlike mango trees, for which nitrogen is not so critical. In relation to phosphorus, this nutrient is usually not applied to avocado nor mango crops, unless there would be a very specific deficiency. With regards to potassium, both crops are quite demanding, as it is a key nutrient to convey sugar to the fruit – resulting in larger and vigorous fruits. Another relevant parameter to be considered in the field trials is the electrical conductivity in the water used for irrigation. Mango trees are more tolerant than avocado trees. In fact, mango trees can tolerate up to 2,000 – 2,500 µS/cm, whereas avocado trees are more sensitive and show negative effects with EC of 1,500 µS/cm and above.

For the development and calibration of the Smart Fertigation Tool, and also to evaluate the agronomic potential of reclaimed water, three different fertigation treatments (T1, T2 and T3) are considered in the comparative analysis (cf. **Figure 28**).

Figure 28. Scheme of fertigation treatments applied in avocado and mango trees.

The scheme is replicated in both avocado and mango plots. Therefore, each of the three treatments is applied to 20 avocado trees and 20 mango trees.

- T1 – Control treatment using local water and mineral fertilisation (n=20). This treatment represented common practice in the region.
- T2 – Treatment with reclaimed water, without mineral fertilisation (n=20). This treatment provides information on the effect of reclaimed water on crops and how far agronomic needs of crops are met without use of additional mineral fertilisers.

- T3 – Treatment with reclaimed water applying the Smart Fertigation Tool currently under development (n=20).

Figure 29. Avocado and mango plots.

The following scheme represents the solution process and establishment of the test site, comparing local common practice of fertigation (T1) in agriculture against the P2GreenN approach (T3).

Figure 30. Scheme of experimental site and solution process.

Fertilising avocado and mango crops is crucial to ensure healthy growth and optimal fruit production. Both crops have specific nutrient requirements that must be addressed to prevent deficiencies that could impact fruit yield and quality.

These needs are influenced by various factors such as soil type, agronomic practices, and the harvest cycle. In general terms, the objective is to replenish the nutrients

utilized by the tree during its growth and fruit production, aiming to avoid both nutritional deficiencies and over-fertilisation that could be detrimental to the plant and soil, including the risk of leaching contamination.

Nutrient requirements for the initial establishment of avocado and mango plantations are determined through a combination of bibliographic data and the extensive expertise of TROPS' technical department, which boasts over 40 years of experience in fertilisation management for these crops.

In general, both avocado and mango require application of primary macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium), secondary macronutrients (calcium and magnesium), as well as doses of micronutrients, with the most critical being iron, zinc, copper, manganese, and boron.

The supply of these nutrients is carried out according to the specific needs of the crop during the growing cycle, identifying periods of higher demand or requirement based on tree physiology.

In the Axarquía region, the fertilisation campaigns for avocado and mango are represented in the following **Table 7**.

Table 7. Fertilisation campaigns for avocado and mango crops

	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May.	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
Avocado												
Mango												

Regarding fertilisation in the pilot, mineral fertilisers have been applied only in Treatment 1. Treatment 2 has received reclaimed water, while Treatment 3 has not yet been established since AgriSmart Data is currently calibrating the nutrient sensors according to the planning. The list of fertilisers applied in the first campaign are described in the following **Table 8**.

Table 8. Fertilising products applied to avocado and mango crops during fertilisation campaign

Product	Crops	Application in avocado (kg or L per ha)	Application in mango (kg or L per ha)
Potassium nitrate fertiliser 13-0-46	Avocado and mango	374.0	40.6
Ammonium nitrate fertiliser 34.5%	Avocado and mango	352.0	162.3
Calcium nitrate fertiliser 15.5-0-0-26	Mango		121.7
Nitrogen fertiliser 21%	Avocado	120.0	
Iron chelate fertiliser EDDHA at 6%	Avocado and mango	8.0	23.2
Boron fertiliser 17.5%	Avocado	17.6	
Calcium fertiliser	Avocado and mango	80.0	115.9

To carry out precise agronomic management of nutrients, it is necessary to conduct at least one foliar analysis of the crop in each growing season. This analysis informs us of the nutrient content in the leaves and allows us to adjust the fertilisation plan based on the results obtained.

Figure 31. Collection of leaves in mango trees for foliar analysis

For avocado and mango, samples were taken in autumn-winter, from leaves developed during spring growth. In our pilot, samples were collected on December 1, 2023, taking one sample from each line of trees, consisting of a combination of leaves from the entire line, resulting in two samples per treatment (cf. **Figure 31**).

The results from the foliar analysis and the interpretation of the parameters will be included in Deliverable 2.5 “Report on the methods used to determine agroecological impacts” which is due in M24 (30 November 2024).

Nevertheless, it has been observed that overall all macro and micronutrient values are within the expected range for both crops, except for sodium and chlorine, which are significantly higher in plants irrigated with reclaimed water (Treatment 2). This is due to the salt content present in this source of water, with electrical conductivity values that in many cases have exceeded the tolerance thresholds of avocado and mango crops. However, except in extreme cases (at the beginning of the trial), we have decided not to dilute the reclaimed water because it reflects the situation faced by most farmers in the area, and one of the goals for the pilot is to be representative of the region's reality.

During the first growing season, a significant incidence of wind in the avocado planting area was observed, especially during the windiest months. Avocado trees are sensitive to wind, especially during their early stages of growth. High winds can lead to physical

damage to the trees, including broken branches and uprooting, which can significantly impede their development and reduce yield potential.

Additionally, wind can exacerbate water stress in avocado trees by increasing transpiration rates, leading to dehydration and negatively impacting overall plant health. Moreover, windbreaks can also help reduce the spread of airborne pests and diseases, which can be particularly detrimental in avocado orchards. By providing a barrier against strong winds, a windbreak can limit the movement of pests and pathogens, helping to maintain a more stable and pest-free environment for avocado trees.

Within the randomized block design, the row most exposed to wind belonged to Treatment 2. Consequently, in this row (line 1), which has experienced 6 losses, the detrimental effects of both wind and salinity have been compounded. It has been noted that warm and dry winds can exacerbate foliar burns, further worsening the loss of photosynthetic surface area in affected plants.

By installing a windbreak (cf. **Figure 32**), these effects will be mitigated, creating a more favourable microclimate that promotes healthier tree growth and improved fruit production for the next years of the field trial.

Figure 32. Windbreaks installed at the test site to protect avocado plants

A soil sampling campaign was carried out in March 15th 2024 to assess the effect on soil of irrigation with reclaimed water (cf. **Figure 33**). Several parameters were analysed including soil humidity, electrical conductivity, organic matter and carbon, P, N, K and other micronutrients.

Figure 33. Soils samples taken in avocado and mango plots

The results from the soil analysis and the interpretation of the parameters will be included in Deliverable 2.5 “Report on the methods used to determine agroecological impacts” which is due in M24 (30 November 2024).

Maturity of Smart Fertigation Tool

The main goal is to develop a digital tool that initially provides information on the levels of the main nutrients and elements in the soil that most affect the growth of plants and in a second phase that will manage to control the dosage of fertilisers or mixture of water sources automatically.

To do this, the iTelemeter V3 equipment allows the connection of sensors and transducers that provide information on multiple parameters and can also manage irrigation and fertilization automatically, based on the actual levels in the roots of the plants.

To achieve this objective, AgriSmart Data is testing and calibrating the sensors that will allow us to read the necessary parameters, which are:

- Tensiometric measurement: current physical force of water retention in the soil.
- Volumetric measurement: the percentage of water in a given amount of soil.
- Environmental and root temperature at different depths.
- Electrical conductivity (EC) of the soil at different depths.
- pH of the soil in roots at different depths.
- NPK concentrations in soil at different depths.

The information on the different parameters will be displayed in real time on any computer or phone device with internet access.

iTelemeter is an IoT (Internet of Things) solution that continuously analyses up to 24 parameters per iTelemeter device and acts based on the algorithms that are

programmed and at the same time puts all the information on servers for visualization and storage.

Currently, there are 6 iTelemeters installed at the test site and it is foreseen that 4 additional iTelemeters will be installed. At the same time, the online platform to display data has been upgraded after several versions and it is now accessible.

The web-based platform informs now about the humidity levels in the soil in real time through the data collected from the tensiometers installed in the soil at 20, 60 and 90 cm depth in avocado and mango crops. The time span between data released by the tensiometers has been increased from 60 to 180 seconds. The graphs depicted indicate the number of centibars registered in the different tensiometers for a specific period of time to be selected by the user. The readings in centibars indicate the tension with which the water is retained in the soil, while successive measurements allow us to determine how quickly the plant is extracting water and how quickly the soil is drying, estimating the most appropriate frequency for irrigation.

Preview Graph

Figure 34. iTelemeter platform with graphs of humidity levels in soil registered by tensiometers in avocado and mango crops

In relation to irrigation management, iTelemeter analyses measurement variables using digital tensiometers at different depths (20 cm, 60 cm and 90 cm) and with automatic operation it will execute the irrigation processes in a very precise way - according to the real needs of the trees. These very precise irrigation episodes will allow controlling the depth of water percolation, controlling the dispersion of nutrients and making irrigation very efficient.

The installation of the last tensiometers has allowed the irrigation system (either using reclaimed water or local water) to be fully automatic now - based on the data collected from the tensiometers. For this, several irrigation set points have been programmed with the iTelemeter so that irrigation episodes are triggered when humidity in soil reaches a certain level (e.g., 35 cbar in mango and 25 cbar in avocado).

On the other hand, the installation of a second mineral fertiliser deposit for addition of fertilisers (during the fertilisation campaigns) is in process as well as the new structure for the fertiliser deposit. The initial objective was to have two different deposits for mineral fertilisers, one for avocado and another one for mango crops. The programming of automatic fertiliser management will follow after the installation of the second deposit. Consequently, at the moment the addition and injection of mineral fertilisers to crops under Treatment 2 must be done manually, using the only deposit installed for fertilisation of both crops. This also means that someone must go in person to the test site and activate/disactivate the pump to add fertilisers whenever required.

Figure 35. Installation of one deposit for application of mineral fertilisers

iTelemeter will also allow, in an initial phase, to control the EC level of reclaimed water and automatically make decisions to lower the conductivity (if necessary) through continuous analysis of the conductivity levels at source and in the soil.

For example, if the sensors detect a high level of EC in roots that may be harmful to plants, iTelemeter will make the decision to decrease the conductivity level of the irrigation water as much as possible by mixing it with local water or any other water source with lower EC. The same will be done with the different key parameters, such as nutrients, being measured, until reaching a smart automation that is much advanced and verified by continuous analysis of soil extractions.

To do so, a prototype automatic management system for water electrical conductivity is currently under development at laboratory scale for the control and mixing of water sources (i.e., reclaimed water and local water) for later installation and application in the smart fertigation treatment (Treatment 3). Once further developed at lab scale, this system will be brought to the test site.

In sum, the following components of the Smart Fertigation Tool have already been installed, namely: lysimeters, tensiometers and electrical sensors for NPK, humidity, EC, pH and temperature. The electrical sensors have also been connected with IoT controllers (iDatacloud and iTelemeter).

Figure 36. Tensiometers (left), lysimeters (middle) and iTelemeter components installed (right).

The last tensiometers in mango fields have been installed recently and connected to the iTelemeter (digital platform for telemetry). The rest of tensiometers in mango and avocado plots have been periodically revised and minor issues with transducers performance have been solved.

The installation of a new sensor's station in line 5 of avocado plot (corresponding to Treatment 2 with reclaimed water) has been planned but not installed yet. It will include lysimeters and tensiometers.

The installation of additional nutrient sensors in avocado and mango plots is foreseen. The incorporation into the telemetry server of the values measured by these sensors is also foreseen – even if values are not reliable yet.

Considering the electrical sensors currently installed in the test site, at the moment we are able to retrieve data of 16 parameters. The final goal is to increase the number of parameters monitored with the SFT up to 30 parameters by the end of P2Green, including not only NPK content, humidity or EC, but also irrigation time, duration of irrigation episodes, volume of water applied, etc.

However, in order to calibrate the electrical sensors, there is ongoing lab and field work required. In parallel, a thorough monitoring campaign of local water, reclaimed water, harvested crops and soil for calibration has been established.

The calibration process with sensors is currently on-going and it will require additional trials synchronising the addition of mineral fertiliser to crops and the analysis of water samples from lysimeters the same day. The goal is to start incorporating the readings of different parameters to the iTelemeter and the web-based platform, such as electrical conductivity, relative humidity and temperature.

Besides optimising the amount of nutrients and water applied to crops, the Smart Fertigation Tool will prevent environmental pollution by controlling potential N and P leaching into the groundwater.

Challenges with scaling up and lessons learnt in the Spanish pilot region

Several challenges and obstacles have been identified since the pilot implementation started. We have divided these obstacles and pain points to consider in two, a) those related to the implementation of the Smart Irrigation Tool, and b) challenges for water reclamation in our pilot.

A) In relation to the Smart Fertigation Tool:

- The calibration of electrical sensors in order to source reliable data on actual levels of nutrients in the soil is an iterative learning-by-doing process, time-consuming and tedious task combining lab and field work
- The calibration is at the same time conditioned by many variables simultaneously (e.g., temperature affecting electrical conductivity)
- Variability of specific crops and frequency of data provided

B) With regards to water reclamation:

- It relies on the adequate treatment performance of raw wastewater at the municipal WWTP
- High electrical conductivity and chloride content in municipal wastewater can be an issue – especially in coastal areas
- A real time monitoring of certain microorganisms (e.g., E. coli) will prevent peaks and levels exceeding maximum acceptable values
- Public acceptance (negative perception associated to its use – unless no other choice)

In terms of raw wastewater collection, treatment and reuse, the following challenges are identified:

Table 9. Identified challenges and barriers of the Spanish pilot region rated by their perceived dimensions (red = higher and green = lower barrier).

	Tech	Acceptance	Financial Incentive
Collection at source	Existing sewage system and infrastructure connected to WWTP	No issue	Requested by regulation
Treatment	Tertiary treatment system validated and available in the market (TRL9)	Questions on risk management plan, pathogens, costs per m ³ , etc.	Treatment costs higher than using local water (but cheaper than desalinated water)
Reuse	Reclaimed water production done, but Smart Fertigation Tool in development (TRL6)	Certain reluctance from farmers (unless no other choice)	None

In relation to the presence of micropollutants in reclaimed water, the (EU) 2020/741 regulation (Annex II) mentions that additional requirements may be imposed following a risk assessment for specific supplies. In particular, heavy metals, pesticides, disinfection by-products and micropollutants are mentioned in the text. However, no specific compounds and maximum values are identified in the regulation, since the minimum quality requirements do not refer to the above mentioned elements. The Risk Management Plan to be undertaken within P2Green will hopefully shed light on the relevance of these parameters in our pilot and determine any further considerations.

Governance readiness level for the Axarquía model

With the recent implementation of the regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse, there is a common European legal framework for all member states with provisions to use reclaimed water in agriculture. The regulation contains strict requirements for the quality of reclaimed water and its monitoring. However, although this regulation will be directly applied in each national context, there are a variety of existing regulations in the Spanish and Andalusian context that should be updated. The regulation is providing guidance and assurance to farmers and consumers - with high water quality standards to meet. But complying with other new obligations, such as the submission of a Risk Management Plan, is challenging. This is indeed tackled in P2Green, as one of our governance solutions foreseen is the preparation of such a Risk Mitigation Plan for the Axarquía pilot.

A revision of current Spanish regulation on water reuse (i.e. Royal Decree 1620/2007) is therefore needed in order to adapt to the provisions of the (EU) 2020/741 regulation. Likewise, the procedures for granting licenses to users of reclaimed water shall also be adapted to the new situation by the regional government of Andalusia and water basin authorities, which have the competence for licensing water reuse permits. A revision of the existing legal framework shall be conducted by national and regional actors.

As mentioned, the new EU Regulation includes the implementation of water risk management plans. Requirements are high for farmers and medium for food chain actors. The reason is that farmers consider these requirements to negatively impact the economics of water reuse, while food chain actors consider they are useful to create trust among final consumers.

Thus, it is necessary to adapt national and regional legislation to the provisions of the (EU) 2020/741 regulation, but also develop guidelines to support users of reclaimed water (mainly farmers) to adopt the provisions and meet the standards required by the new legal framework.

The definition of regional governance instruments in P2Green will be done together with the local public authorities (AXARAGUA, Algarrobo municipality, Malaga province). The reclamation of wastewater addresses the high risk of droughts in the region and adds up with ecological benefits by reducing the demand for mineral fertiliser as well as the emission of N & P to water bodies, thereby contributing to fulfil the requirements of the Water Framework Directive. The approach has the potential to be widely adapted in southern Spain as well as in the majority of the Mediterranean countries but also in other water-scarce regions throughout Europe.

In P2Green, the transferability will be facilitated by defining financial aspects related to water reclamation, securing the compliance with (EU) Regulation 2020/741 on wastewater reclamation, developing a risk management plan, and creating a strategic plan on extending the use of reclaimed water including societal acceptance.

3 Action plan

Milestone 5, "Technology implemented" was originally set for May 2024. However, the project is in the process of an amendment, due to their above explained specific challenges, and anticipates reaching this milestone by March 2025. Comprehensive reflections and detailed reports are thereby slated for the progress report on system readiness (D1.2) in month 30 and the demonstration report on validated prototypes (D1.1) in month 36. **Table 10** shows the tasks and deliverable dates and how they are proposed to be impacted by the on-going amendment.

Table 10. Overview of tasks and deliverable dates and how they are proposed to be impacted by the on-going amendment

Work Package No	Task No	Task Name	Lead Beneficiary	Start Month	End Month	Related Deliverable	Deliverable Due Date	Due Date (as of amendment)
WP1	T1.1	Set up, operation, demonstration and validation in pilot regions	S360, EVH, BioA	1	48	D1.1 D1.6	31 May 2025 30 Nov 2023	30 Nov 2025 31 May 2024
WP1	T1.2	Mature existing innovations towards higher TRL at systems level	SLU	15	36	D1.2 D1.3	30 Nov 2024 30 Nov 2025	31 May 2025 30 Nov 2025
WP1	T1.3	Blueprints towards circular N&P flows	BioA	1	24	D1.4	30 Nov 2024	31 May 2025
WP1	T1.4	Cross-fertilisation	BioA	1	48	D1.5	30 Sep 2026	30 Sep 2026
WP1	T1.1	Milestone 1: Planning for the implementation of each technology system in all three pilot region is completed	S360, EVH, BioA	1	12	--	30 Nov 2023	31 May 24
WP1	T1.1	Milestone 5: Technology in all three pilot regions is implemented to study the dynamic interfaces between rural/coastal and urban/industrial environments	S360, EVH, BioA	1	18	--	31 May 24	31 Mar 25

The internal project plan, presented as Gantt charts, was established and continually updated in collaboration with pilot partners (cf. ANNEX). Monitoring tools for Key

Performance Indicators (KPI) and Governance Readiness Level (GRL) charts have been developed.

The Swedish pilot aims to collect 150 m³ of urine by 2026, producing over one ton of dry fertiliser for barley cultivation. Challenges include encouraging urinal use and exploring partnerships with municipalities, event organizers, and housing complexes to expand urine collection.

Termination of partner EVH impact Aurin production, prompting partner restructuring measures of the North German Plain pilot region with the anticipated integration of the KWB. The VunaNexus urine treatment plant, is underway to advance to TRL 7. Field trials are on-going in reduced scale and with external recycling fertilisers, in close alignment with the public authority.

The Spanish pilot focuses on advancing an integrated irrigation fertigation system, targeting TRL 8 by project end. Activities include sensor testing, calibration, and expanding lysimeter use. Biofertiliser production and irrigation targets are progressing, albeit with adjustments. Coordination includes advancing Governance Readiness Level with specific indicators such as Risk Management Plan and adapting regulations.

3.1 Sweden implementation

The goal is to have collected during P2Green's runtime a total of 150 m³ of urine and reached a collection rate of 100 m³/year by 2026 (cf. Table 11. **Key Performance Indicators for the Swedish pilot region and** progress planned. With this urine, the aim is to produce over one ton of dry fertiliser which will be used to fertilize 35 000 kg of barley, resulting in the production of 50 000 litres of beer. The drying technology is currently at TRL 6 and aims to reach TRL 8 by 2026.

One of the challenges is that people are not using the urinals. SLU and S360 are currently testing and developing other ways to modify conventional chemical toilets to become urine-diverting. In addition, S360 is in conversation with a few different stakeholders about implementing our urine concentrator technology in permanent settings within the upcoming years. These developing partnerships include municipalities, large event organisers, airports and existing urine-diverting housing complexes.

With the mentioned partnerships forming, we are confident that we will be able to expand the urine collection and achieve our goals. Already in 2024, 11 m³ of urine has been collected thanks to working with a big event, Valboug, in Uppsala on April 30th with Toabolaget's 41 urinals.

Figure 37. As of May 2024, 11 m³ of urine has already been collected in Sweden together with SLU, S360 and Toa Bolaget (external project partner). The total goal for 2024 is 25 m³.

Table 11. Key Performance Indicators for the Swedish pilot region and progress planned.

KPI Name	Description	Aim in project	Start	End goal	Goal 2024 (actual)	Goal 2025	Goal 2026
TRL (overall)	Recycling of source-separated urine through chemical stabilization and evaporation.	Implementation at larger scale, integration into circular value chains	5	8	TRL: 6 (TRL=6)	TRL: 7	TRL: 8
Collection of urine	Expansion of collection through partnerships with Touch Down and other partnerships	By end, collect over 150 m ³ of urine in total	<5 m ³ /yr	>150 m ³ total	25 m ³ /yr (11 m ³)	50 m ³ /yr	100 m ³ /yr
Fertiliser production	To produce a dry concentrated fertiliser from human urine that is tailored for growing barley for beer production.	Increase from small-scale (<50 kg/yr) to large-scale (>1 ton/yr) fertiliser production.	<50 kg/yr	>1 ton/yr	1000 kg/yr	2000 kg/yr	4000 kg/yr
Malted Barley production	Mass of malted barley produced	Increase from 20 kg to 35 000 kg	20 kg	35 000 kg	3 600 kg	9 000 kg	35 000 kg

3.2 Germany implementation

Based on the above-mentioned developments at EVH, the production of sufficient Aurin for the field trials (9,5 m³) has been at risk. In terms of guaranteeing the execution of the

agronomic and ecological research, recycling fertilisers KIT and Aurin have been sourced from zirkulierBAR project and abroad VunaNexus production plants respectively. A nitrite sensor patented by Eawag, and licensed to VunaNexus is currently TRL 4 and under development by a high-profile strategic partner. It is currently being developed in the laboratory and will be tested in operational environments in the second half of the year 2024 with the goal of reaching TRL 7. This development is part of an innoSuisse project running in parallel. Major steps to mature the system towards a fully modular system are focused on reducing costs and improving the automation (software). A distiller will be installed during the summer, allowing to concentrate the product up to 25 times. This element is part of the cost reduction goal, as it is a new cheaper technology replacing the expensive stainless steel by PEHD plastic. This should also open doors in the future to the usage of external heat recovery in order to reduce energy consumption for the concentration and hygienisation step.

For the Vagtshoff/Goldeimer the next actions planned for the validation of the value chain are to optimise the operations of the container-based composting process and the fertilization. The biological process demands a narrow and consecutive process monitoring to be able to optimise the process towards TRL 7.

As mentioned, the administrative decision reduced the size of the planned field trials. Hence, further iterations with the authority will be needed to reach the target of a large-scale field trial.

Table 12. Key Performance Indicators of the pilot region North German Plain and progress planned.

KPI Name	Description	Aim in project	Unit	Current Stage	End of Project goal	Goal 2024	Goal 2025	Goal 2026
TRL (urine treatment)	Recycling of source-separated urine	Implementation at larger scale		6	8	6	7	8
Collection of urine	Scaling up from house-scale to neighborhood-scale	200 inhabitants will collect approximately 100 m ³ /yr urine	m ³ /yr	35	100	100	40	110
Aurin production	Liquid fertiliser production	Large-scale fertiliser production	m ³ /yr	0	7,7	9,5	10	10
TRL (feecal composting)	Recycling of source-separated feaces through sanitisation and composting	Automation & integration into closed value chains		5	7	6	7	7

Solid fertiliser production	Produced amount of solid fertiliser	Fertiliser used to grow crops on Vagtshoff farm.	t/yr	0	40	18,5	16	14
Rye & Barley production	Surface area of cultivated barley with both fertilisers	Apply all fertiliser produced	ha	0	10	0,16	4,56	4,56

3.3 Spain implementation

One of the key objectives of the Spanish pilot is to advance and further develop an innovative integrated fertigation system which is adapted to the use of reclaimed water, reaching a TRL8 by the end of the P2Green project.

As the Water Reclamation Plant used to produce reclaimed water in the pilot is already a validated and demonstrated technology (TRL9), this key objective will be achieved by focusing on developing the Smart Fertigation Tool and Decision Support System for the control and optimization of nutrients and irrigation using reclaimed water.

In this sense, the goal is to continue advancing during 2024 and move from the current TRL6 (technology demonstrated in relevant environment) to reach a TRL7 (system prototype demonstrated in operational environment) in 2025 and TRL8 (system complete and qualified) in 2026 (cf. **Table 13**).

Table 13. Key Performance Indicators related to TRL in the Spanish pilot and progress planned.

KPI Name	Description	Aim in project	Current Stage	End of Project goal	Goal 2024	Goal 2025	Goal 2026
TRL (OVERALL)	Water Reclamation Plant (WRP) with Smart Irrigation Tool and DSS integrated	Advance in TRL of integrated irrigation system adapted to the use of reclaimed water generated by the Water Reclamation Plant (tertiary treatment)	9 (WRP), 6 (irrigation system)	8	6	7	8
TRL (water reclamation plant)	WRP (tertiary treatment instead of RichWater system)	Use of Water Reclamation Plant (tertiary treatment) instead of RichWater (MBR, ETV verified) due to lower requirement of reclaimed water production	9	9	9	9	9
TRL (irrigation system)	Smart Irrigation Tool and Decision Support System for nutrients and irrigation control	Advance in TRL of integrated irrigation system adapted to the use of reclaimed water: irrigation system supplemented by a nutrient monitoring tool to optimise fertilisation and to avoid over-fertilisation of crops irrigated with reclaimed water	6	8	6	7	8

To do so, the iTelemeter equipment and the sensors responsible for controlling irrigation are already installed and operational. The process that has been followed with nutrient sensors is based on a first phase where sensors were tested in the laboratory by carrying out tests with reclaimed water, drinking tap water and distilled water. These tests contributed to verify the sensitivity and responses to the different elements in the water. It has also been possible to verify the variations produced by the soil's temperature in the results obtained. However, this testing and calibration phase needs to continue until there is a complete control of the variable ground temperature. Afterwards, real time data of macronutrients present in soil will be integrated in the iTelemeter.

On the other hand, lysimeters have been installed successfully. Lysimeters are devices to extract soil percolating water and they will be used to carry out water extractions. There are a series of lysimeters available for extractions at different points on the plots. Additional and continued samples using the lysimeters are needed to obtain reliable data of certain parameters in soil at different depths (20 cm, 60 cm and 90 cm) and calibrate the electrical sensors.

Extractions are done simultaneously with the dosage of nutrients and irrigation, with the aim of adjusting the sensor values to the real ones. It is therefore necessary to continue working on these sensors, both in the laboratory and on the field, with the final objective of adjusting the values provided as close as possible to the real ones analysed. Finally, the installed nutrient sensors will be providing information on the moments in which a fertilisation is provided, reacting very differently to normal irrigation with only water.

The fertigation system also requires further development, such as installation of second deposit for application of mineral fertilisers and the programming of automatic fertiliser management.

Last but not least, the prototype automatic management system for water electrical conductivity is currently under development at laboratory scale. This is a crucial component for the control and mixing of water sources used for irrigation (i.e., reclaimed water and local water) and it should be installed and applied in the smart fertigation treatment (Treatment 3) to further develop the Smart Fertigation Tool.

Other relevant KPI established in the Spanish pilot relate to the volume of biofertiliser production. The target of producing up to 10 m³/day of reclaimed water has already been achieved and it is expected to continue through the project. There is also a target to reach 1 hectare of surface with the irrigated crops (mango and avocado crops). Due to the limited dimension of the existing test site, it will not be possible to reach this target. Currently, approximately 838 m² are dedicated to cultivation of 120 mango and avocado crops on site. This deviation will, however, not present an issue from the point of view of advancing the TRL of the Smart Fertigation Tool. The field test has been designed so that the three different fertigation treatments are established and tested in each type of crop, every treatment is also duplicated for optimal scientific rigour, and the

number of trees per treatment (i.e., 20 trees) is well representative. Nevertheless, the opportunity to test the Smart Irrigation Tool with soil samples from other plots in the proximities will be explored, therefore increasing the variability of soils and crops considered.

Table 14. Additional Key Performance Indicators related to TRL in the Spanish pilot and progress planned.

Indicator name	Description	Aim in project	Current Stage	End of Project goal	Goal 2024	Goal 2025	Goal 2026
TRL (irrigation system)	Smart Fertigation Tool and Decision Support System for nutrients and irrigation control	Advance in TRL of integrated irrigation system adapted to the use of reclaimed water: the irrigation system will be further supplemented by a nutrient monitoring tool to optimise fertilisation	6	8	6	7	8
Biofertiliser production	produce nutrient-rich effluent that complies with national/EU regulation for the use in agriculture (category 2.3)	During P2GreeN, enough quantity of reclaimed water will be generated to irrigate 120 avocado and mango trees	10 m ³ /d	up to 10 m ³ /d	10 m ³ /d	10 m ³ /d	10 m ³ /d
Surface of irrigated crops	Surface area of cultivated avocado and mango crops	1 hectare	838 m ²	1 ha	838 m ²	838 m ²	838 m ²

Other indicators of high relevance internally established at pilot level relate to the number of fertigation treatments demonstrated, reaching the target of 3 treatments in 2024, once the electrical sensors are sufficiently calibrated to initiate the T3 treatment.

Another indicator related to the number of avocado and mango tree plants. So far, the target of having 120 trees for testing has been reached.

The number of parameters and values provided by the Smart Fertigation Tool is also expected to increase, from 16 parameters available at the moment, to 28 parameters at the end of 2024 and up to 30 parameters at the end of P2GreeN.

Table 15. Relevant indicators internally established by Spanish pilot and progress planned.

Indicator name	Description	Aim in project	Current Stage	End of Project goal	Goal 2024	Goal 2025	Goal 2026
Fertigation treatments	comparison of fertigation treatments using local water, reclaimed water, mineral fertilisers	Demonstration of three adjusted fertigation treatments	2 treatments	3 treatments	3 treatments	3 treatments	3 treatments
Avocado & mango trees	Number of trees of each type used in field test	120 trees in total (60 trees each species)	120 trees	120 trees	120 trees	120 trees	120 trees
Parameters (Smart Fertigation Tool)	Number of parameters monitored with Smart Irrigation Tool	30 parameters	16	30	28	30	30

Very important for the Spanish pilot is also to coordinate an action plan to advance in the Governance Readiness Level (GRL) on the region. For this, four different indicators have been established, namely:

- Risk Management Plan according to EU Regulation 2020/741
- Adaptation of Spanish Royal Decree 1620/2007
- Roadmap to extend the use of reclaimed water in the Axarquía region
- Guidelines for authorities to implement adequate water pricing and tariff structure

With the active collaboration and contribution from other P2Green partners (i.e., SustChem, ICLEI, IRS), the goal is to advance from the current GRL3-4 up to GRL7 by the end of the project, providing the specific plans, policy recommendations, and guidelines.

4 References

Baresel, C., Andersson, S., Yang, J. and Andersen, M.H. (2016). Comparison of nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions calculations at a Swedish wastewater treatment plant based on water concentrations versus off-gas concentrations. *Advances in Climate Change Research* 7(3), 185-191.

Beckinghausen, A., Odlare, M., Thorin, E., & Schwede, S. (2020). From removal to recovery: An evaluation of nitrogen recovery techniques from wastewater. In *Applied Energy* (Vol. 263, p. 114616). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114616>

Bengtsson, M., & Tillman, A.-M. (2004). Actors and interpretations in an environmental controversy: The Swedish debate on sewage sludge use in agriculture. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 42(1), 65–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2004.02.004>

Brodin, T., Fick, J., Jonsson, M., Klaminder, J. (2013). Dilute concentrations of a psychiatric drug alter behaviour of fish from natural populations. *Science*, 339, 814-815.

Carstensen, J., Andersen, J. H., Gustafsson, B. G., Conley, D. J. (2014). Deoxygenation of the Baltic Sea during the last century. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111 (15), S. 5628–5633.

Chojnacka, K., Moustakas, K., & Witek-Krowiak, A. (2020). Bio-based fertilisers: A practical approach towards circular economy. *Bioresource Technology*, 295, 122223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.122223>

Codispoti, L. A. (2010). Interesting Times for Marine N₂O. *Science* 327 (5971), S. 1339–1340

Demissie, N., Simha, P., Lai, F. Y., Ahrens, L., Mussabek, D., Desta, A., & Vinnerås, B. (2023). Degradation of 75 organic micropollutants in fresh human urine and water by UV advanced oxidation process. In *Water Research* (Vol. 242, p. 120221). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120221>

Esculier, F., & Barles, S. (2020). Past and Future Trajectories of Human Excreta Management Systems: Paris in the Nineteenth to Twenty-First Centuries. In N. Flipo, P. Labadie, & L. Lestel (Eds.), *The Seine River Basin* (Vol. 90, pp. 117–140). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-407>

Eurofins. (n.d.). Analys av slam och vatten i REVAQ. Eurofins Environment Testing Sweden AB. <https://www.eurofins.se/media/681694/revaq.pdf>

Project Number:

101081883

Project Acronym:

P2Green

Deliverable 1.6

European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, Fribourg-Blanc, B., Dhuygelaere, N., Madec, C. (2022). 11th technical assessment on UWWTD implementation, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/915400>

European Commission, Eurostat. (2023a). Eurostat regional yearbook : 2023 edition, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2785/606702>

European Commission. (2023b). Organic farming in the EU – A decade of organic growth, January 2023. European Commission, DG Agriculture and Rural Development, Brussels. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/agri-market-brief-20-organic-farming-eu_en.pdf

European Commission. (2023c). Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023SC0158s>

Eurostat. (2020). Disposal of sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment by method of disposal, 2020. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/3/35/Fig_4_-_Disposal_of_sewage_sludge_from_urban_wastewater_treatment_by_method_of_disposal%2C_2020_%28%25_of_total%29.png

FAO. (2015). To feed our people we must first feed our soil. Africa Fertiliser. <https://www.fao.org/3/bq928e/bq928e.pdf>

Ferguson, D. T. (2014). Nightsoil and the 'Great Divergence': Human waste, the urban economy, and economic productivity, 1500–1900. *Journal of Global History*, 9(3), 379–402. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1740022814000175>

Forsberg, J. (2022). PFAS in a Swedish wastewater treatment plant - An analysis of the effectiveness of major treatment steps on 33 PFAS. Masters Thesis at Luleå University of Technology, Department of Civil, Environmental and Natural Resources Engineering.

Glibert, P. M., Maranger, R., Sobota, D. J., & Bouwman, L. (2014). The Haber Bosch–harmful algal bloom (HB–HAB) link. *Environmental Research Letters*, 9(10), 105001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/10/105001>

Grizzetti, B., Vigiak, O., Udias, A., Aloe, A., Zanni, M., Bouraoui, F., Pistocchi, A., Dorati, C., Friedland, R., De Roo, A., Benitez Sanz, C., Leip, A., & Bielza, M. (2021). How EU policies could reduce nutrient pollution in European inland and coastal waters. *Global Environmental Change*, 69. <https://doi-org.ludwig.lub.lu.se/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102281>

Hammer, M., Clemens, J. (2007). A tool to evaluate the fertiliser value and the environmental impact of substrates from wastewater treatment. *Water Science and Technology*, 56(5), 201–209.

Harder, R., Wielemaker, R., Larsen, T. A., Zeeman, G., & Öberg, G. (2019). Recycling nutrients contained in human excreta to agriculture: Pathways, processes, and products. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 49(8), 695–743.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2018.1558889>

HELCOM. (2013). Summary report on the development of revised Maximum Allowable Inputs (MAI) and updated Country Allocated Reduction Targets (CART) of the Baltic Sea Action Plan. This document was prepared for the 2013 HELCOM Ministerial Meeting to give information on the progress in implementing the HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan. Helsinki: HELCOM.
<http://www.helcom.fi/Documents/Ministerial2013/Associated%20documents/Supporting/Summary%20report%20on%20MAI-CART.pdf> Retrieved: (12.09.2014).

Jansson, T., Andersen, H. E., Gustafsson, B. G., Hasler, B., Höglind, L., & Choi, H. (2019). Baltic Sea eutrophication status is not improved by the first pillar of the European Union Common Agricultural Policy. *Regional Environmental Change*, 19(8), 2465–2476.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01559-8>

Jodar-Abellan, A.; López-Ortiz, M.I.; Melgarejo-Moreno, J. (2019). Wastewater Treatment and Water Reuse in Spain. Current Situation and Perspectives. *Water* 2019, 11, 1551.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/w11081551> <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/11/8/1551#:~:text=Since%202008%2C%20and%20according%20to,as%20the%20total%20treated%20water>

Johansson, M., Kvarnström, E. and Stintzing, A.R. 2009. Going to Scale with Urine Diversion in Sweden – From Individual Households to Municipal Systems in 15 Years. *Global Dry Toilet Association of Finland*.

Jordbruksverket (2022). Övergödning och läckage av växtnäring.
<https://jordbruksverket.se/jordbruket-miljon-och-klimatet/overgodning-och-lackage-av-vaxtnaring>

Jönsson, H., Stenström, T.-A., Svensson, J., Sundin, A. (1997). Source separated urine-nutrient and heavy metal content, water saving and faecal contamination. *Water science and technology*, 35(9), 145-152.

Jönsson, H., Stintzing, A.R., Vinneras, B., Salomon, E. (2004). Guidelines on the Use of Urine and Faeces in Crop Production. Stockholm Environment Institute.

Jönsson, H. (2011). Recycle all plant nutrients in the wastewater – not only phosphorus! The Swedish Research Council Formas.

Königer, J., Lugato, E., Panagos, P., Kochupillai, M., Orgiazzi, A., & Briones, M. J. I. (2021). Manure management and soil biodiversity: Towards more sustainable food systems in the EU. *Agricultural Systems*, 194, N.PAG. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103251>

Landeshauptstadt Hannover (2016). Abwassersatzung für die Landeshauptstadt Hannover. Stadtentwässerung Hannover (SEH).

Larsen, T.A., Lienert, J., Joss, A., Siegrist, H. (2004). How to avoid pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 113(1-3), 295-304

Larsen, T.A., Lienert, J., Udert, K. (2013). *Source Separation and Decentralization for Wastewater Management*. IWA Publishing, London. ISBN 9781843393481

Levén, L., Gros Calvo, M., Dalahmeh, S., Ljung, E., Lundin, G., Ahrens, L., Wiberg, K., Jönsson, H., Eveborn, D. (2016). Läkemedel i källsorterat klosettavatten och latrin – behandling och risker (In Swedish). JTI.

Lienert, J., Bürki, T., Escher, B.I. (2007). Reducing micropollutants with source control: substance flow analysis of 212 pharmaceuticals in faeces and urine. *Water Sci. Technol.* 56 (5), 87e96.

Luo, Y., Guo, W., Ngo, H.H., Nghiem, L.D., Hai, F.I., Zhang, J., Liang, S., Wang, X.C. (2014). A review on the occurrence of micropollutants in the aquatic environment and their fate and removal during wastewater treatment. *Science of The Total Environment*, 473-474, 619-641.

Sadia, M., Mahmood, A., Ibrahim, M., Kashif Irshad, M., Hassan Ali Quddusi, A., Bokhari, A., Mubashir, M., Fatt Chuah, L., Loke Show, P. (2022). Microplastics pollution from wastewater treatment plants: A critical review on challenges, detection, sustainable removal techniques and circular economy. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, Volume 28, 102946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2022.102946>.

Mayor, Á., Beltran, E., Cortina, J. L., & Valderrama, C. (2023). Nitrogen flow analysis in Spain: Perspectives to increase sustainability. *Science of the Total Environment*, 858, N.PAG. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160117>

Menegat, S., Ledo, A., & Tirado, R. (2022). Greenhouse gas emissions from global production and use of nitrogen synthetic fertilisers in agriculture. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 14490. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-18773-w>

Mårald, E. (2000). *Cycles of Earth (Jordens kretslopp)*, Umeå University. (in Swedish), Umeå, Sweden.

Narain, S. (2002). The flush toilet is ecologically mindless. *Down to Earth*, 10(19). https://www.susana.org/_resources/documents/default/2-199-narain-2002-flush-toilet-ecological-mindless-en.pdf

- Naturvårdsverket. (2021). Ammoniak, utsläpp till luft. <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/data-och-statistik/luft/utslapp/ammoniak-utslapp-luft/>
- Parfitt, N. (2023). Centering Farmer Perspectives on a Dry-Fertiliser Made from Human Urine: A case study on Gotland, Sweden. Master Thesis Series in Environmental Studies and Sustainability Science, No 2023:012, Lund University. <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?func=downloadFile&recordId=9117215&fileId=9117219>
- Pistocchi, A., Grizzetti, B., Nielsen, P. H., Parravicini, V., Steinmetz, H., Thornberg, D., & Vigiak, O. (2023). An Assessment of Options to Improve the Removal of Excess Nutrients from European Wastewater. In *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* (Vol. 234, Issue 9). Springer Science and Business Media LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06478-3>
- Ramírez, C. A., & Worrell, E. (2006). Feeding fossil fuels to the soil: An analysis of energy embedded and technological learning in the fertiliser industry. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 46(1), 75-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2005.06.004>
- Reijnders, L. (2014). Phosphorus resources, their depletion and conservation, a review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 93, 32–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2014.09.006>
- Senecal, J. and Vinnerås, B. 2017. Urea stabilisation and concentration for urine-diverting dry toilets: Urine dehydration in ash. *Science of The Total Environment* 586, 650–657.
- Senecal, J., Nordin, A.C., Decrey, L., Kohn, T. and Vinnerås, B. 2022. Fate of Parasites and Viruses in Calcium Hydroxide-Treated Urine in Relation to Temperature and Moisture Content. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 10.
- Simha, P., Senecal, J., Gustavsson, D.J.I. and Vinnerås, B. (2020a). Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering. Katakai, R., Pandey, A., Khanal, S.K. and Pant, D. (eds), pp. 205-221, Elsevier.
- Simha, P., Lalander, C., Nordin, A., & Vinnerås, B. (2020b). Alkaline dehydration of source-separated fresh human urine: Preliminary insights into using different dehydration temperature and media. *Science of the Total Environment*, 733. <https://doi-org.ludwig.lub.lu.se/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139313>
- SOU. (2020). Hållbar slamhantering (2020:3). Statens Offentliga Utredningar. <https://www.regeringen.se/contentassets/3d68880d2e6942f3a1dccb158e46beb7/hallbarslamhantering-sou-20203/>
- Spink, W.W. (1979). *Infectious Diseases : Prevention and Treatment in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries*, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, UNITED STATES.

SRU. (2015). Stickstoff - Lösungsstrategien für ein drängendes Umweltproblem. Sondergutachten des Sachverständigenrat für Umweltfragen. https://www.umweltrat.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/02_Sondergutachten/2012_2016/2015_01_SG_Stickstoff_HD.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2

Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S. E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., Carpenter, S. R., De Vries, W., De Wit, C. A., Folke, C., Gerten, D., Heinke, J., Mace, G. M., Persson, L. M., Ramanathan, V., Reyers, B., & Sörlin, S. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, 347(6223), 1259855. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1259855>

Statista. (2023a). Volume of municipal wastewater produced in Europe in 2020, by country. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1393764/wastewater-treatment-generation-europe/>
Statista. (2023a). Global fertiliser demand by nutrient 2011-2022 [Data set]. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/438930/fertiliser-demand-globally-by-nutrient/>

Statista. (2023b). Medium term forecast for global fertiliser demand to 2025/2026, by nutrient [Data set]. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/438964/medium-forecast-fertiliser-demand-globally-by-nutrient/>

Sutton, M.A., Bleeker, A., Howard, C.M., Bekunda, M., Grizzetti, B., de Vries, W., van Grinsven, H.J.M., Abrol, Y.P., Adhya, T.K., Billen, G., Davidson, E.A., Datta, A., Diaz, R., Erisman, J.W., Liu, X.J., Oenema, O., Palm, C., Raghuram, N., Reis, S., Scholz, R.W., Sims, T., Westhoek, H. and Zhang, F.S. (2013). Our Nutrient World: The challenge to produce more food and energy with less pollution, Centre for Ecology and Hydrology on behalf of the Global Partnership on Nutrient Management and the International Nitrogen Initiative, Edinburgh.

Söderholm, K., Vidal, B., Hedström, A., & Herrmann, I. (2023). Flexible and Resource-Recovery Sanitation Solutions: What Hindered Their Implementation? A 40-Year Swedish Perspective. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 30(1), 23–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2022.2100212>

Trimmer, J. T., & Guest, J. S. (2018). Recirculation of human-derived nutrients from cities to agriculture across six continents. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(8), 427–435. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0118-9>

Tuholske, C., Halpern, B.S., Blasco, G., Villasenor, J.C., Frazier, M., Caylor, K. (2021). Mapping global inputs and impacts from of human sewage in coastal ecosystems. *PLoS ONE* 16(11): e0258898. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258898>

Vinnerås, B., Nordin, A., Niwagaba, C., & Nyberg, K. (2008). Inactivation of bacteria and viruses in human urine depending on temperature and dilution rate. In *Water Research* (Vol. 42, Issue 15, pp. 4067–4074). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2008.06.014>

Project Number:

101081883

Project Acronym:

P2Green

Deliverable 1.6

Van Donk, E., Peacor, S., Grosser, K., De Senerpont Domis, L.N., Lürling, M. (2016). Pharmaceuticals May Disrupt Natural Chemical Information Flows and Species Interactions in Aquatic Systems: Ideas and Perspectives on a Hidden Global Change. in: Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology Volume 238, (Ed.) P. de Voogt, Springer International Publishing. Cham, pp. 91-105.

Wallenberg, P., & Eksvärd, J. (2018). Lantrbrukets syn på kretslopp. LRF.
<https://www.macrosystem.se/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Lantbrukets-syn-p%C3%A5-kretslopp.pdf>

Water Reuse Europe (2020). The state of the sector. <https://www.water-reuse-europe.org/the-state-of-the-sector/#page-content>

WHO and UNICEF (2017). Progress on Drinking Water, Sanitation and Hygiene: 2017 Update and SDG Baseline, World Health Organization (WHO) and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), Switzerland.

WHO and UNICEF (2022). State of the World's Sanitation: An urgent call to transform sanitation for better health, environments, economies and societies. New York: United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and the World Health Organization. ISBN: 978-92-4-001447-3

WISE (2023). Freshwater Information System for Europe.
<https://water.europa.eu/freshwater/europe-freshwater/water-reuse>

Yadav, K. D., Tare, V., & Ahammed, M. M. (2010). Vermicomposting of source-separated human faeces for nutrient recycling. Waste Management, 30(1), 50–56.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.09.034>

Contact

Programme Coordinator:

agrathaer GmbH

Eberswalder Straße 84, 15374 Müncheberg

Tel.: +49 33432 82 149

Info@agrathaer.de

www.p2green.eu

www.facebook.com/p2greenHorizonEU

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/p2green-horizon-eu-72aba1259/>

www.instagram.com/p2green/

www.twitter.com/P2green_Horizon

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No°101081883. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.